

RUSTIK database system (D2.4)

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This report presents the final version and datasets of the RUSTIK Viewer, including its architecture and system specifications. It analyses the scope and main objectives of the system, as well as the importance of examining Europe-wide datasets alongside locally collected data. Finally, it outlines the sustainability and maintenance plan for the Viewer.

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	DMP	Data management plan	

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	SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	

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Part A

1. Introduction & Report Approach

1.1. Report Structure

This deliverable presents the final development of the RUSTIK Data System and its implementation within the RUSTIK Viewer¹. It provides a comprehensive overview of the system architecture, datasets, and operational framework supporting the analysis of rural transitions across Europe.

The report is structured into two complementary parts.

→ **Part A** provides a comprehensive and structured description of the RUSTIK Data System, covering its conceptual foundations, technical architecture, data organisation, and operational framework. It establishes the basis for understanding how the system has been designed, implemented, and prepared for long-term use.

The section begins by defining the scope, objectives, and methodological approach of the system, clarifying its role in supporting the analysis of rural transitions across socioeconomic, environmental, and digital dimensions. It explains how the data infrastructure is conceived to bridge different territorial scales, enabling the integration of European-level datasets with locally generated information.

Building on this, the report presents a detailed overview of the system architecture, describing the interaction between its core components. This section highlights the modular design of the system, ensuring scalability, interoperability, and ease of maintenance.

Part A then examines in depth the structure and composition of the RUSTIK datasets. It distinguishes between the European Core dataset, based on harmonised and comparable indicators derived from institutional sources, and the Living Lab datasets, which provide highly contextualised, place-based data collected through experimental and participatory methodologies. The report details how these two data components are integrated into a unified analytical framework, enabling multi-scalar analysis and supporting both European-level monitoring and local-level interpretation.

A dedicated section is also included to describe the technical specifications and functionalities of the RUSTIK Viewer. This includes the organisation of geospatial layers, the interaction tools available to users, and the mechanisms that enable data exploration, visualisation, and comparison across territories. Emphasis is placed on the usability of the platform and its capacity to translate complex datasets into accessible and actionable information.

¹ The RUSTIK viewer is available online at www.rustik-he.eu/data-viewer.

Furthermore, Part A outlines the quality control framework implemented within the system. It describes the procedures adopted to ensure data consistency, accuracy, and coherence across all indicators, as well as the technical validation processes applied to guarantee system stability and performance. This includes both one-off structural actions and recurring activities aimed at maintaining high standards over time.

Finally, the section presents the sustainability and maintenance plan, detailing the technical and organisational measures established to ensure the long-term operability of the system. It defines the processes for data updates, system monitoring, documentation management, and continuous improvement, ensuring that the RUSTIK Viewer remains functional, reliable, and relevant beyond the duration of the project.

- **Part B** provides a detailed presentation of the indicators included in the RUSTIK Viewer. Each indicator is described through concise and structured explanations, supported by visual material to facilitate interpretation. This section is designed to enhance usability and transparency, enabling users to clearly understand the content, structure, and relevance of the data available within the platform.

1.2. Scope and objectives

The RUSTIK dataset system is designed to support the analysis of rural transitions across Europe. Its scope includes the collection, organisation, and integration of data that reflects the socioeconomic, environmental, and digital dimensions of territorial change. By bringing together information from different governance levels and thematic domains, the system provides a structured knowledge base to better understand ongoing transformations in rural territories.

The system is built to achieve four primary goals:

- **Data Provision & Integration.** To provide suitable data for rural transitions, creating regional and local databases that are integrated into existing portals and contribute to a European-level framework with common indicators.
- **Functional Analysis (FRA).** To provide quantitative data for the discussion of the five rural functions defined by RUSTIK (ecological, infrastructure, land-based products, diversified production, and social capital), helping planners pinpoint "service deserts" or high-value ecological areas requiring protection.
- **To support local Strategic Reflection in EU rural areas.** To support what-if scenarios. By overlaying digital infrastructure with socioeconomic data, policymakers can assess the effectiveness of investments, such as broadband, in supporting talent retention or identifying where further interventions are needed. Layers in the Tool can be overlapped for cross-sectional analysis.
- **Testing innovative assessment methods. Bridging the Qualitative Gap.** Unlike traditional GIS systems, RUSTIK incorporates also perception-based data from Living Lab experiments (e.g., neighbourhood safety, walkability, or community trust). This aligns physical infrastructure planning with the lived experience of residents, fostering higher legitimacy in local governance.

Together, these objectives ensure that the RUSTIK system supports both large-scale policy monitoring and local-level analysis, creating a coherent framework that connects European strategies with territorial realities. In this way, the system facilitates the exchange of knowledge between territories and strengthens the capacity of institutions and stakeholders to interpret and respond to rural change.

The main benefits include:

- **Evidence-Based Governance.** Improved quality of planning decisions through quantitative evidence and systematic monitoring of development objectives.
- **Collaborative Capacity.** The system facilitates the exchange of knowledge between territories and strengthens the capacity of institutions to interpret and respond to rural change, promoting active cooperation between European, regional, and local actors.
- **Enhanced transparency** in rural governance by providing open and accessible territorial data, allowing stakeholders, policymakers, and citizens to better understand rural dynamics and policy outcomes.

1.3. Approach

The RUSTIK database system brings together two complementary domains: the European Core database and the Living Lab database. Each serves a distinct role, and together they create a multi-level framework for understanding rural and regional transitions across Europe.

- The European Core database provides a **harmonised set of indicators that cover all European regions in a consistent way**. It includes data on socioeconomic, environmental, and digital transitions, ranging from demographic change, employment, education, and income levels to land use, biodiversity, climate risks, renewable energy, and digital connectivity.

The strength of the European Core database lies in its comparability and scope. It enables cross-country analysis, highlights territorial disparities, and positions local or regional contexts within the wider European picture.

Beyond its analytical role, the European Core database provides a robust reference framework for external stakeholders. It supports benchmarking across regions, facilitates the monitoring of progress towards European policy objectives, and allows users to identify structural trends and territorial imbalances in a consistent and standardised manner across the EU.

- The Living Lab database, developed within the RUSTIK project, complements this broad perspective with **place-based detail**. Each of the 14 Living Labs gathers specific datasets tailored to its local realities, often at the scale of municipalities, districts, or neighbourhoods. These datasets capture information not usually available at European level, such as land ownership patterns, farm structures, migration flows by age group, service accessibility at community level, digital infrastructure at household level, or quality of life indicators based on local surveys.

This approach enables a more precise understanding of territorial dynamics, bringing forward issues that remain invisible in aggregated European datasets. The Living Labs integrate local knowledge, perceptions, and sector-specific data into the analysis, supporting the design of solutions adapted to specific territorial contexts.

In addition, the Living Lab datasets provide methodological value by illustrating how locally generated data can complement European statistical sources, contributing to more flexible and context-sensitive approaches to rural data governance.

Beyond their role within the RUSTIK project, the Living Lab datasets provide significant added value for external users, including policymakers, researchers, and territorial planners. Their main contribution lies in their ability to complement European-scale indicators with high-resolution, context-specific evidence that supports more informed and targeted decision-making.

- From a **socioeconomic perspective**, Living Lab data enables a deeper understanding of local demographic dynamics, labour market structures, service accessibility, and social cohesion, supporting the identification of territorial disparities and service gaps.
- From an **environmental perspective**, the datasets provide detailed insights into land use patterns, local resource management, and environmental pressures, enabling more precise assessments of sustainability and climate resilience at local scale.

- From a **digital transition perspective**, Living Lab data offers a realistic picture of connectivity conditions and infrastructure performance, helping to identify digital divides and guide targeted investments.

Overall, the Living Lab component transforms the RUSTIK Viewer into a decision-support tool that bridges European policy frameworks with on-the-ground realities, enabling external stakeholders to move from general analysis to actionable, place-based strategies.

When used together, the European Core and Living Lab databases do more than provide information at different scales. Their integration constitutes a bridge between policy-oriented datasets and community-based evidence, linking strategic priorities with practical insights. This combined system strengthens the capacity to design interventions that are both measurable at European level and meaningful at local level, ensuring that knowledge flows in both directions: from European policy to local implementation, and from local evidence to strategic decision-making.

Figure 1 RUSTIK Data Viewer overview. Source. <https://rustik-he.eu/data-viewer/>

2. RUSTIK Data System Overview

2.1. System Architecture

The RUSTIK Data System integrates multiple sources of information into a unified platform that supports the analysis of rural and regional transitions across Europe. It combines data from European institutions with data produced within the Living Labs, creating a consistent framework that links European-level evidence with locally generated knowledge.

The system is composed of two main databases:

- European-level database, which compiles existing secondary data from European agencies and programmes. These datasets provide harmonised and comparable indicators covering socioeconomic, environmental, and digital dimensions.
- Living Lab databases, which gather qualitative and quantitative data collected directly by RUSTIK partners and place-based actors. This includes locally produced information, field observations, and novel quantitative sources such as geo-data scraping and big data.

These databases are integrated within the RUSTIK Information System, which functions as a bridge aligning standardised European indicators with locally contextualised data, ensuring coherence across different territorial scales.

Through this structure, the RUSTIK Data System supports the exploration, visualisation, and interpretation of information within the RUSTIK Viewer.

In the figure below, the conceptualization of the Rustik Data Viewer is presented. Data produced internally by the Rustik partners are highlighted in red.

RUSTIK Data Viewer: Conceptualization

Figure 2 RUSTIK Data Viewer conceptualization.

2.2. Structure of the RUSTIK database

The RUSTIK database is organized as a multi-layered information system designed to overcome the chronic data scarcity that traditionally limits rural policymaking.

To date, the system hosts a comprehensive repository of 372 active indicators.

Its structure brings together harmonized statistical datasets, spatial information, and locally collected evidence within a unified analytical framework.

Table 1 Distribution of Indicators by Core.

Dataset	Indicator size
Core European Dataset	91 harmonised indicators across three transition themes (Socioeconomic, Environmental, and Digital).
Living Lab Dataset	281 place-based indicators from 14 pilot regions (in the frame of an LL approach) representing different European contexts

2.3. Core European Dataset

The European component is built from secondary and open-access data sources managed by recognized European and international institutions (e.g., Eurostat, Copernicus, JRC). This core layer comprises exactly 91 harmonized indicators, strategically distributed to reflect the overarching European policy priorities:

- Socioeconomic Transition (52 indicators): This is the most robust block, providing longitudinal data on population dynamics, employment structures, education levels, gender equality (such as the FemDI index), and accessibility to general services.
- Environmental Transition (37 indicators): Focuses on land cover, biodiversity, air quality, and climate resilience, incorporating advanced spatial grids to monitor wildfire risks and precipitation changes.
- Digital Transition (2 indicators): Captures the fundamental baseline of rural connectivity through indicators tracking the spatial availability of high-speed fixed and mobile broadband networks.

This structure ensures strict coherence across thematic dimensions. It provides the necessary macro-baseline that enables cross-country benchmarking and ensures that local dynamics can be compared against European averages and policy frameworks.

Table 2 Distribution of Indicators by Transition and Indicator Class.

Transition	Indicator Class	N° Indicators
Socioeconomic Transition	Demographics and Population	4
	Social Welfare and Inclusion	6
	Facilities and Community Development	27
	Employment and Economic Development	14
	Community Engagement and Governance	1
<i>Total</i>		52
Environmental Transition	Climate Resilience	7
	Natural Resources and Heritage Conservation	7
	Land Cover and Land Use	20
	Sustainable Development	3
<i>Total</i>		37
Digital Transition	Digital infrastructure	2
<i>Total</i>		2
<i>Total</i>		91

The European Core database of the RUSTIK Data Viewer is built upon a set of harmonised datasets provided by recognised European institutions, research centres, and open-data platforms. These sources ensure the reliability, comparability, and spatial consistency of the indicators used to analyse rural transitions across Europe. By relying primarily on official statistics and established European data services, the system guarantees methodological coherence and alignment with European policy monitoring frameworks.

Emphasis has been placed on the use of datasets that are harmonised at European scale and regularly updated by institutional providers such as Eurostat, the European Environment Agency, the Joint Research Centre, and Copernicus services. These sources offer consistent territorial coverage and standardized methodologies, making it possible to compare indicators across countries and regions while maintaining a robust statistical foundation for analysis. In parallel, complementary sources such as OpenStreetMap or specialised research initiatives contribute additional spatial information that enhances the analytical capacity of the system.

The combination of these datasets forms a coherent and interoperable data ecosystem. As illustrated in Table 3, each source contributes to specific thematic domains and indicator groups within the three transition themes. This structured approach ensures that the RUSTIK database

integrates diverse types of information while maintaining a clear link between data providers, indicator categories, and the analytical objectives of the platform.

Table 3 Data Sources by Transition Theme.

Socioeconomic Transition		
This theme includes indicators on demographics, population change, employment, education, migration, accessibility of services, and gender equality. Data sources include:		
Data Source	Description	Thematic groups
Eurostat	The statistical office of the European Union. It provides official, harmonized, and comparable statistics across EU Member States to support planning, monitoring, and evaluation of EU policies.	Demographic data
		Labour market indicators
		Education levels
		Migration population
DG REGIO	The department of the European Commission responsible for the EU's cohesion policy. It manages structural funds and supports regional development, territorial cooperation, and the reduction of regional disparities.	Female Disadvantage Index (FEMDI)
		Female Achievement Index (FEMAI)
ESPON Profecy	The European platform or project focused on the development and use of functional territorial typologies, helping to classify and analyse spatial patterns to inform territorial and cohesion policies	Accessibility to services and facilities
Joint Research Centre / DGREGIO	A collaboration between the JRC and DG REGIO to develop scientific tools and analyses in support of regional policy, including spatial indicators, scenarios, and territorial modelling.	Economic activity
		Employment structure
		GDP per capita
		Tourism capacity
Joint Research Centre – LUISA	LUISA (Land-Use-based Integrated Sustainability Assessment) is a territorial modelling platform developed by the JRC. It simulates land-use dynamics and supports the	Land use
		Land cover
		Built areas

	assessment of policy impacts on land, environment, and development.	Forests
		Agriculture
University of Gothenburg	An EU agency providing independent environmental information. It supports the development and evaluation of environmental policies through monitoring of climate change, pollution, biodiversity, and more.	Quality of Government Index at NUTS 2 level
OpenStreetMap (OSM)	The global collaborative project that creates free and editable maps. It provides open-source geospatial data widely used in research, planning, and application development.	Points of interest across multiple domains
Environmental transition		
Indicators address land cover, ecosystems, biodiversity, climate resilience, and energy production. Data sources include:		
European Environmental Agency (EEA)	The EU agency providing independent environmental information. It supports the development and evaluation of environmental policies through monitoring of climate change, pollution, biodiversity, and more.	Air quality (PM2.5, PM10, ozone)
		Wildfires
		Climate change projections (precipitation patterns, drought frequency).
Copernicus Global Land Service	Part of the EU's Copernicus programme, this service delivers global environmental data on land cover, vegetation, hydrology, and more using satellite imagery, supporting monitoring and policy decisions.	Urban atlas
		Coastal zones
		Grasslands
		Forests
		Impervious surfaces
		Tree cover density
		Biodiversity-relevant datasets

Eurostat	The statistical office of the European Union. It provides official, harmonized, and comparable statistics across EU Member States to support planning, monitoring, and evaluation of EU policies	Degree of Urbanization.
Joint Research Centre	The European Commission's science and knowledge service. It provides independent scientific and technical advice to support EU policies through research, data modelling, scenario analysis, and tool development.	Renewable energy production (solar, onshore, hydropower).
Digital transition		
The digital transition theme focuses on connectivity and infrastructure. Data sources include:		
Eurostat	The statistical office of the European Union. It provides official, harmonized, and comparable statistics across EU Member States to support planning, monitoring, and evaluation of EU policies	Access to high-speed broadband (fixed and mobile networks)

The Living Lab Data Ecosystem

While the European Core provides the broad picture, the Living Lab Dataset acts as the project's primary mechanism for uncovering the invisible dynamics of rural areas. It introduces 281 highly contextualized, place-based indicators sourced directly from the 14 pilot regions.

Data are produced by RUSTIK partners and local actors, covering diverse territorial contexts, from remote mountainous regions to peri-urban agricultural belts. Crucially, this dataset goes beyond traditional statistics by incorporating innovative methodologies such as participatory GIS mapping, web scraping, and qualitative surveys.

Indicators vary according to local priorities, providing unprecedented granularity in areas such as:

- **Demographic and Social Dynamics.** Migration flows disaggregated by specific age groups and local perceptions of quality of life and community trust.
- **Land and Agricultural Micro-Data.** Deep dives into land ownership patterns, CAP payment distribution among smallholders, and local food supply chains.
- **Economic Vitality.** Mapping of active vs. empty commercial premises, local commuting rates, and the prevalence of rural self-employment, including rural entrepreneurship and entrepreneurial networks.

- **Accessibility and Quality of Life.** Spatial analysis of service proximity (health, education, and administration) combined with localized environmental indicators—such as acoustic pollution and air quality—and community-based metrics including energy efficiency.
- **Community engagement Qualitative.** insights from local surveys and participatory mapping that capture civic engagement levels, trust in regional administrations (EQI), and the self-organizing capacity of rural communities.
- **Digital and Infrastructure Realities.** Actual broadband speeds experienced at the household level, contrasting the theoretical coverage provided by the European dataset.

Data collection within the Living Labs combines official statistics, local administrative records, and field-based or survey data, allowing the integration of standardised and context-specific information.

While European indicators provide a baseline for comparison, the unique value of the RUSTIK project lies in the ability of its 14 Living Labs to act as on-the-ground data laboratories. These laboratories have implemented experimental methodologies to capture rural realities that are often invisible to official statistics, transforming local actors into primary sources of information.

The specific sources and methods developed within the Living Lab experiments are detailed below:

- **Collective Intelligence and PPGIS.** The Living Labs of Sant Miquel de Balenyà (ES) and Monmouthshire (UK) have turned citizens into "human sensors" through the use of Participatory Geographic Information Systems (PPGIS) and the Maptionnaire platform. This approach has generated georeferenced data on the perception of quality of life, safety, and accessibility to services, capturing the lived experience of residents.
- **Data Extraction from the Invisible Economy.** To overcome the lack of updated business registries, the (RS) and Troyan–Apriltsi–Ugarchin (BG) Living Labs utilized web scraping techniques and participatory mapping of supply chains. These sources enable the inventory of small local producers and market flows that do not typically appear in national statistical databases.
- **Integration of High-Resolution Administrative Records.** Several Living Labs successfully integrated granular institutional sources that are normally not harmonized at the European level. For instance, Galicia (ES) cross-referenced detailed cadastral and biophysical data to prioritize the recovery of model settlements, while in Bulgaria, Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) payment records at the municipal level were used to analyse the actual impact of agricultural funding.
- **Real-Time Monitoring via AI.** The Gloucestershire (UK) Living Lab developed dashboards powered by Artificial Intelligence. This source integrates internal datasets from service organizations to dynamically identify service deserts, allowing for a significantly more agile policy response than that provided by decennial census data.

- **Qualitative and Experiment-Based Evidence.** Living Labs also generate critical data through direct interaction, such as study visits to model farms in Świętokrzyskie (PL) or focus groups with youth in Rhein-Hunsrück (DE). These sources provide thick data on institutional trust, barriers to entrepreneurship, and factors for retaining young talent in rural areas.
- **Integration of IACS and Collaborative Data.** In Nockregion–Oberkärnten (AT), the official Integrated Administration and Control System (IACS) was combined with OpenStreetMap and Google Maps. This cross-referencing, validated with municipal directories, made it possible to map small rural businesses (SRB) that do not appear in standard commercial registers.

By structuring these local sources alongside European data, the RUSTIK Viewer ensures that rural transition policies are grounded not only in global metrics but also in the technical, social, and perceived reality meticulously documented by the Living Labs.

2.4. System Specification

The RUSTIK Data Viewer is an online GIS platform that allows users to interactively explore the territorial indicators and datasets collected within the framework of the RUSTIK project. The platform provides access to information structured in geospatial databases and indicator tables, enabling the visualization of the territorial distribution of socioeconomic, environmental, and demographic variables relevant to the analysis of rural transitions across Europe.

All information is organized within a web-based geographic information system built according to OGC standards. The system integrates reference cartography, territorial units, and multiple thematic layers linked to the project's analytical domains. Through this structure, the viewer enables the spatial representation of indicators, the consultation of attributes associated with each territorial unit, and the comparison of territorial patterns across different European regions and the Living Labs participating in the project.

The platform combines cartographic visualization with data exploration tools, facilitating the interpretation of indicators through interactive thematic maps and spatial query functionalities. In this way, the viewer acts as an interface to the project's data infrastructure, supporting the analysis of the geographical distribution of indicators and the assessment of territorial dynamics and transition processes in European rural areas.

The viewer has been designed with a user-friendly and intuitive interface that facilitates the interpretation of results for different types of users, ranging from technical staff to decision-makers. Its visual design and organizational logic are inspired by the RUSTIK conceptual framework, ensuring graphical and functional consistency with other materials developed within the project.

The platform is built on a modular **open-source architecture**, designed to maximize interoperability while minimizing long-term maintenance costs. This architecture implements a robust spatial data infrastructure that integrates several core components:

- **Spatial Database.** A centralized PostgreSQL/PostGIS repository storing all territorial indicators and enabling complex spatial queries.
- **Map Server.** GeoServer, responsible for publishing geospatial data through international OGC standards such as WMS and WFS.
- **API Middleware.** Modular PHP REST APIs (Visualization and Manager) that manage data processing, metadata handling, and system logic.
- **Web GIS Viewer.** An interactive frontend developed with HTML5, JavaScript, and OpenLayers for data exploration and visualization.
- **Security and Management.** Authentication layers based on token systems that regulate user roles and access to the platform.

To ensure scalability and performance, the backend follows a **decoupled architecture**. The Visualization API optimizes the delivery of spatial data from GeoServer to the frontend, while the Manager API manages metadata and administrative tasks. This structure ensures that even complex geospatial queries remain responsive for the end user.

Figure 3 Functional architecture diagram of the RUSTIK Viewer.

The database is organized as a layered system combining interactive tools and thematic information, allowing users to move smoothly between general overviews and detailed analyses depending on their needs. The platform therefore supports multiple levels of data exploration through several interactive functionalities, including:

- **Area Draw Tool.** Allows users to create custom areas for spatial analysis.
- **Measure Tool.** Enables distance measurement directly on the map.
- **Information Tool.** Provides access to detailed attributes associated with specific map elements.
- **Zoom Functionality.** Allows navigation from local details to the full European territorial extent.
- **Data Layers.** Thematic layers that can be activated, combined, or compared to generate different analytical perspectives.

Through this architecture and functionality set, the RUSTIK Data Viewer provides a flexible environment for exploring territorial data and supporting evidence-based analysis of rural transitions across Europe.

3. RUSTIK Dataset

3.1. European Dataset

The European dataset constitutes the common analytical backbone of the RUSTIK Data System and provides a harmonised set of indicators designed to analyse and compare territorial dynamics across European regions. It supports the study of the three main transition dimensions addressed by the project by integrating indicators derived from institutional European data sources and standardized statistical datasets.

One of the key characteristics of this dataset is the **diversity of spatial scales** at which indicators are available. Data are provided across multiple territorial levels, including NUTS (levels 0 to 3), LAU units, and grid-based spatial data. This multi-scalar structure enables analyses that range from broad European comparisons to more detailed spatial assessments of territorial patterns, such as the distribution of services, environmental features, or accessibility conditions.

The indicators also differ in terms of **territorial coverage and data availability**. While some datasets, particularly those derived from harmonised European statistics, provide full coverage across EU countries or the wider European space, others include a more limited set of countries. These variations reflect differences in the availability of source data, the methodologies used by the data providers, and the spatial nature of the underlying datasets.

From a technical perspective, the European dataset integrates **different types of indicators and data structures**. Some indicators consist of aggregated statistical variables associated with administrative units, such as demographic trends, labour market structures, or educational attainment. Others derive from geospatial datasets, including raster layers and high-resolution spatial grids, which are particularly relevant for environmental analysis and land-use monitoring. Additionally, certain indicators are based on **points of interest and accessibility metrics**, combining spatial datasets and infrastructure information to represent the availability and proximity of services and facilities across territories.

In the tables below, the three components of the European Core Dataset and the 91 indicators they contain are presented in detail. For each indicator, the scale, unit, and territorial coverage are specified. More detailed information on the indicators, including their description, source of origin, access links, and year of development, is available within the Rustik Viewer, as shown in figure 4.

Figure 4 Additional Indicator Information in the Rustik Viewer.

- Socioeconomic Transition

This section includes a wide range of indicators covering population dynamics, labour market structures, education, social inclusion, migration, and accessibility of key services.

All the data inside the Socio-economic Transition are presented below.

Table 4 Socioeconomic Indicators by Domain, Scale and Territorial Coverage.

Domain				Indicator	Scale	Unit	Territorial coverage	
Socioeconomic Transition	Demographics and Population	Population		Total Population (2021) / (2011) / (2001) / (1991) / (1981)	Lau 2	Thousands (k)	EU27 + EFTA – Iceland	
				Population growth (2011-2021)	Lau 2	Crude rate of total population change	EU27 + EFTA – Switzerland	
		Population density		Population Density (2021)	Lau 2	Inhabitants/km ²	EU27 + EFTA – Iceland	
				Density Growth (2011-2021)	Lau 2	Crude rate of total population change / km ²	EU27	
	Social Welfare and Inclusion	Gender		Women employment proportion	Nuts 2	Percentage (%)	EU27	
				Women and Men unemployment difference	Nuts 2	Percentage (%)	EU27	
				Female Disadvantage Index (FemDI)	Nuts 2	FemDI (1-100)	EU27	
				Female Achievement Index (FemAI)	Nuts 2	FemAI (1-100)	EU27	
	Migration		Crude rate of net migration	Nuts 3	Thousands	EU27		
			Migration population proportion	Nuts 2	Percentage (%)	EU27		
	Facilities and Community Development	Public equipment and facilities	Primary Schools		Points of Interest Primary School	Lau 2	Points	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey
					Grid for Primary Schools Availability	Lau 2	N° accessible within 6.25 km ²	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey – Iceland
				Share Overlaid Accessibility to Primary School	Nuts 3	Minutes (min)	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey	
				Distance to Primary School	Lau 2	Meters (m)	EU27	
		Secondary Schools		Points of Interest Secondary School	Lau 2	Points	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey	
			Grid for Secondary Schools Availability	Lau 2	N° accessible within 6.25 km ²	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey – Iceland		

Domain			Indicator	Scale	Unit	Territorial coverage
			Share Overlaid Accessibility to Secondary School	Nuts 3	Minutes (min)	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey – Bosnia and Herzegovina, Kosovo
			Distance to Secondary School	Lau 2	Meters (m)	EU27
		Hospitals	Points of Interest Hospitals	Lau 2	Points	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey
			Grid for Hospital Accessibility	Lau 2	N° accessible within 6.25 km ²	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey
			Share Overlaid Accessibility to Hospitals	Nuts 3	Minutes (min)	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey – Bosnia and Herzegovina, Kosovo
			Distance to Hospitals	Lau 2	Meters (m)	EU27
		Doctors	Points of Interest Doctors	Lau 2	Points	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey – Bosnia and Herzegovina, Kosovo
			Grid for Doctor Accessibility	Lau 2	N° accessible within 6.25 km ²	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey
		Pharmacies	Points of Interest Pharmacies	Lau 2	Points	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey
			Grid for Pharmacy Availability	Lau 2	N° accessible within 6.25 km ²	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey
		Train Stations	Grid for Train Stations Availability	Lau 2	N° accessible within 6.25 km ²	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey
			Share Overlaid Accessibility to Train Stations	Nuts 3	Minutes (min)	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey – Bosnia and Herzegovina, Kosovo
			Distance to Train Stations	Lau 2	Meters (m)	EU27
		Banks	Points of Interest Banks	Lau 2	Points	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey
			Grid for Bank Accessibility	Lau 2	N° accessible within 6.25 km ²	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey

Domain				Indicator	Scale	Unit	Territorial coverage
			Retail Shops	Points of Interest Retail shops	Lau 2	Points	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey
				Grid for Retail Shops Accessibility	Lau 2	N° accessible within 6.25 km ²	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey
			Cinema	Points of Interest Cinemas	Lau 2	Points	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey
				Grid for Cinema Availability	Lau 2	N° accessible within 6.25 km ²	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey
				Share Overlaid Accessibility to Cinemas	Nuts 3	Minutes (min)	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey – Bosnia and Herzegovina, Kosovo
				Distance to Cinemas	Lau 2	Meters (m)	EU27
	Employment and Economic Development	Job Accessibility		Unemployment Proportion	Nuts 2	Percentage (%)	EU27
				Agriculture Sector Workers Proportion	Nuts 2	Percentage (%)	EU27
				Industrial Sector Workers Proportion	Nuts 2	Percentage (%)	EU27
				Construction Sector Workers Proportion	Nuts 2	Percentage (%)	EU27
				General Service Sector Workers Proportion	Nuts 2	Percentage (%)	EU27
				Financial Service Sector Workers Proportion	Nuts 2	Percentage (%)	EU27
		Economic Activity		Tourism capacity in rooms	Lau 2	Number	EU27
				GDP per cap	Nuts 3	Euros (€)	EU27
		Education		Tertiary education level (25-64) (%)	Nuts 3	Percentage (%)	EU27
				Secondary education level (25-64) (%)	Nuts 3	Percentage (%)	EU27
				Early school leaving (18-24) (%)	Nuts 3	Percentage (%)	EU27
					Forest Proportion of Land (%)	Lau 2	Percentage (%)

Domain				Indicator	Scale	Unit	Territorial coverage
		Sectorial Land Use		Built Proportion of Land (%)	Lau 2	Percentage (%)	EU27
				Agricultural Proportion of Land (%)	Lau 2	Percentage (%)	EU27
	Community Engagement and Governance	Trust in Administrations		Quality of Government Index	Nuts 2	EQI (1-100)	EU27

- **Environmental Transition**

The environmental component of the dataset captures land cover, natural resources, biodiversity, and climate-related risks.

All the data inside the Environmental Transition are presented below.

Table 5 Environmental Indicators by Domain, Scale and Territorial Coverage.

Domain			Indicator	Scale	Unit	Territorial coverage
Environmental Transition	Climate Resilience	Wildfires	Projected change in meteorological forest fire danger	Lau 2	Percentage (%)	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey
			Average meteorological forest fire danger 1981-2010 (MapServer)	Lau 2	UAMV/AverageForestDanger	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey + North Africa & Middle East
			Areas burnt by wildfires	Lau 2	Area	EU27
		Precipitation	Projected changes in heavy precipitation in winter	Lau 2	Percentage (%)	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey + North Africa & Middle East
			Projected changes in heavy precipitation in summer	Lau 2	Percentage (%)	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey + North Africa & Middle East
			Drought Frequency Change 2041-2071 RCP 4.5	Lau 2	Frequency	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey

Domain		Indicator	Scale	Unit	Territorial coverage		
	Natural Resources and Heritage Conservation	Drought Frequency Change 2041-2070 RCP8.5	Lau 2	Frequency	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey		
		Forestal Areas	Forest Type (raster 20 m and 100 m), Europe, 3-yearly	Lau 2	Area	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey	
			Tree Cover Density 2018 (raster 10 m and 100 m), Europe, 3-yearly	Lau 2	Percentage (%)	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey	
			Tree Cover Change Mask (raster 20 m), Europe, 3-yearly	Lau 2	Area	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey	
			Dominant Leaf Type 2018 (raster 10 m), Europe, 3-yearly	Lau 2	Area	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey	
			Protected Areas & Biodiversity	Natura 2000 Protected Areas	Lau 2	Area	EU27
		Emerald Protected Areas		Lau 2	Area	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey - Iceland	
		Mountain Areas		Lau 2	Area	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey	
		Land Cover and Land Use	Land Cover	Urban Atlas Land Cover/Land Use (vector), Europe, 6-yearly	Lau 2	Minimum Mapping Unit (MMU) of 0.25 hectares	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey
				Urban Atlas Land Cover/Land Use Change (vector), Europe, 6-yearly	Lau 2	Land cover type	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey
	CLC+Backbone 2018 (raster 10 m), Europe, 3-yearly			Lau 2	Land cover type	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey	
	Coastal Zones Land Cover/Land Use (vector), Europe, 6-yearly			Lau 2	Land thematic class	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey	
	Coastal Zones Land Cover/Land Use Change 2012-2018 (vector), Europe, 6-yearly			Lau 2	Land thematic class	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey	
	Built-up area		Impervious Built-up 2018 (raster 10 m and 100 m), Europe, 3-yearly	Lau 2	Area	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey	
			Urban Atlas Building Height 2012 (raster 10 m), Europe	Lau 2	Meters (m)	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey	
			Degree of Urbanization	Lau 2	Urbanisation level	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey	
	Imperviousness		Imperviousness Density 2018 (raster 10 m and 100 m), Europe, 3-yearly	Lau 2	Percentage (%)	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey	

Domain		Indicator	Scale	Unit	Territorial coverage		
		Imperviousness Change 2015-2018 (raster 20 m and 100 m), Europe, 3-yearly	Lau 2	Percentage (%)	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey		
		Imperviousness Classified Change (raster 20 m), Europe, 3-yearly	Lau 2	Type of classified change	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey		
		Grassland	Grassland 2018 (raster 10 m and 100 m), Europe, 3-yearly	Lau 2	Area	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey	
			Grassland Change 2015-2018 (raster 20 m), Europe, 3-yearly	Lau 2	Area	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey	
		Agriculture	Agricultural Area (2018)	Lau 2	Area	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey	
		Water	Water and Wetness status 2018 (raster 10 m and 100 m), Europe, 3-yearly	Lau 2	Area	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey	
			Riparian Zones Land Cover/Land Use (vector), Europe, 6-yearly	Lau 2	Area	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey	
			Riparian Zones Land Cover/Land Use Change 2012-2018 (vector), Europe, 6-yearly	Lau 2	Classified change	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey	
		Air Quality	Air quality of Ozone [$\mu\text{g}^*\text{d}/\text{m}^3$]	Lau 2	$\mu\text{m}^*\text{d}/\text{m}^3$	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey	
			Air quality of PM10 [$\mu\text{g}^*\text{d}/\text{m}^3$]	Lau 2	$\mu\text{m}^*\text{d}/\text{m}^3$	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey	
			Air quality of PM2.5 [$\mu\text{g}^*\text{d}/\text{m}^3$]	Lau 2	$\mu\text{m}^*\text{d}/\text{m}^3$	EU27 + UK + EFTA + Western Balkans + Turkey	
		Sustainable Development	Energy	Solar Production	Lau 2	MWh	EU27
				Onshore Production	Lau 2	MWh	EU27
				Hydropower Production	Lau 2	MWh	EU27

- **Digital Transition**

This digital component assesses technological maturity and high-speed connectivity in European regions it is essential for territorial integration into a globalized economy reliant on seamless digital services.

All the data inside the Digital Transition are presented below.

Table 6 Digital Transition Indicators by Domain, Scale and Territorial Coverage.

Domain			Indicator	Scale	Unit	Territorial coverage
Digital Transition	Digital infrastructure	Quality of Digital Service	Access to high-speed mobile network		Mbps	EU
			Access to high-speed fixed network		Mbps	EU

3.2. Living Lab Dataset

The RUSTIK Living Lab Dataset complements the European-level data by providing detailed, place-based information from 14 regional Living Labs across Europe. These Living Labs represent diverse territorial contexts and serve as experimental environments where local realities can be studied in depth. Each Living Lab has produced specific indicators according to its context and the priorities identified locally, which means that the type of information collected varies from region to region.

Unlike the harmonised European dataset, which ensures comparability across countries, the Living Lab dataset captures fine-grained, locally specific data that are often unavailable in pan-European statistics. In some regions, this may include detailed demographic breakdowns or household-level migration flows, while in others it may focus on land ownership, farm structures, or accessibility to essential services. Additional information can also relate to local labour markets, tourism, service provision, broadband coverage, or community perceptions gathered through surveys.

The RUSTIK Living Lab Dataset therefore enables analysis at smaller territorial scales such as municipalities, parishes, or neighbourhoods. By adapting the choice of indicators to local circumstances, it reflects aspects of rural and regional transitions that are not visible at European level. Combined with the Core European Dataset, it ensures that the RUSTIK Data Viewer can connect EU-wide evidence with the data needed to understand territorial diversity and local trajectories.

In the table below, the Living Lab Dataset and the indicators it contains are presented in detail. For each indicator, the scale and unit are specified.

Table 7 Living Lab Indicators by Domain, Scale and Territorial Coverage.

Living lab	Indicator	Scale	Unit
General	Points of Interest for Commercial Activities	Lau 2	Point
	Points of Interest for Culture	Lau 2	Point
	Points of Interest for Health	Lau 2	Point
	Points of Interest for Industry	Lau 2	Point
	Points of Interest for Nature and Forestry	Lau 2	Point
	Points of Interest for Restauration	Lau 2	Point
	Points of Interest for General Services	Lau 2	Point
	Points of Interest for Sports and Leisure	Lau 2	Point
	Points of Interest for Touristic Assets	Lau 2	Point
	Points of Interest for Touristic Information	Lau 2	Point
Galicia (ES) Living Lab	Ratio between landowners and inhabitants at municipal level	Lau 2	Ratio. Total inhabitants/Number of landowners
	Average size of land plot (ha)	Lau 2	Hectares (h)
	Average number of land plots per landowner	Lau 2	Number
	Average amount of land per owner	Lau 2	Number
	Prioritisation of settlements for the implementation of the "model settlement" instrument (Result 1)	Settlements	Priority index
	Prioritisation of settlements for the implementation of the "model settlement" instrument (Result 2)	Settlements	Priority index
	Galicia Living Labs Municipalities	Living Lab	Administrative area
	Galicia Municipalities	Lau 2	Administrative area
Garfagnana - Lunigiana (IT) Living Lab	Average download speed (Mbit/s)	Lau 2	Mbit/s
	Average upload speed (Mbit/s)	Lau 2	Mbit/s
Gloucestershire (UK) Living Lab	Number of connections less than 2Mbit/s (number of lines)	Lau 2	N° of lines
	Full-fibre take-up (% of full-fibre coverage)	Lau 2	Percentage (%)
	Garfagnana and Lunigiana Living Lab	Living Lab	Administrative area
	Garfagnana and Lunigiana Communes	Lau 2	Administrative area
	Gloucestershire Living Lab	Living Lab	Administrative area
Gloucestershire Districts	Lau 2	Administrative area	

Living lab		Indicator	Scale	Unit
North Karelia (FI) Living Lab		Percent of population over 65 years	Living Lab	Administrative area
		Percent of population with foreign mother tongue	Lau 2	Inhabitants
		North Karelia Living Lab	Lau 2	Percentage (%)
		Population	Lau 2	Percentage (%)
Osona - Sant Miquel de Balenyà (ES) Living Lab	Experiment Subdivision	Sant Miquel de Balenyà Living Lab	Living Lab	Administrative area
		Experiment Subdivision	Living Lab	Administrative area
		Seva Divisions	Lau 2	Administrative area
		Osona Municipalities	Lau 2	Administrative area
		Osona Sections	Lau 2	Administrative area
	Service in Osona County	Cultural Point of Interest	Lau 2	Point
		Cultural Heatmap	Lau 2	Density (points/km ²)
		Administrative Point of Interest	Lau 2	Point
		Administrative Heatmap	Lau 2	Density (points/km ²)
		Tourism Point of Interest	Lau 2	Point
		Tourism Heatmap	Lau 2	Density (points/km ²)
		Commercial Point of Interest	Lau 2	Point
		Commercial Heatmap	Lau 2	Density (points/km ²)
		Leisure Point of Interest	Lau 2	Point
		Leisure Heatmap	Lau 2	Density (points/km ²)
		Healthcare Point of Interest	Lau 2	Point
		Healthcare Heatmap	Lau 2	Density (points/km ²)
		Services Point of Interest	Lau 2	Point
		Services Heatmap	Lau 2	Density (points/km ²)
	Indicators	Quality of Life by Neighbourhood	Neighbourhood	Quality of Life Index
		Quality of life Grid Calculation	Neighbourhood	Grid
		Energy Efficiency Certification	Neighbourhood	Point
		Commercial Vitality	Neighbourhood	Point
		Green public space proximity	Neighbourhood	Km

Living lab		Indicator	Scale	Unit	
Experiment Local Perception		Acoustic pollution	Neighbourhood	dB(A)	
		Lack of Space in the Household	Living Lab	Dominant response	
		Neighbourhood Walking Spaces	Living Lab	Dominant response	
		Neighbourhood Dangerous Spaces	Living Lab	Dominant response	
		Neighbourhood Noisy Spaces	Living Lab	Dominant response	
		Urban Landscape Quality	Living Lab	Dominant response	
		Neighbourhoods Climate Shelters	Living Lab	Dominant response	
		Neighbourhoods Climate Shelters Responses	Living Lab	Dominant response	
		Very Low Quality of Life	Living Lab	Dominant response	
		Low Quality of Life	Living Lab	Dominant response	
		Average Quality of Life	Living Lab	Dominant response	
		Very Good Quality of Life	Living Lab	Dominant response	
		Courses Participation - Yes	Living Lab	Dominant response	
		Courses Participation - No	Living Lab	Dominant response	
		Associations Participation - Yes	Living Lab	Dominant response	
		Associations Participation - No	Living Lab	Dominant response	
		EMD Following - No	Living Lab	Dominant response	
		All EMD Following - Yes	Living Lab	Dominant response	
		App EMD Following - Yes	Living Lab	Dominant response	
		Gallaret EMD Following - Yes	Living Lab	Dominant response	
		Social Media EMD Following - Yes	Living Lab	Dominant response	
	Osrednjeslovenska (SI) Living Lab		Local Products Consumption - No	Living Lab	Dominant response
			Local Products Consumption - Occasional	Living Lab	Dominant response
			Local Products Consumption - Yes	Living Lab	Dominant response
Osrednjeslovenska (SI) Living Lab		Osrednjeslovenska Living Lab	Living Lab	Administrative Area	
		Osrednjeslovenska Municipalities	Lau 2	Administrative Area	
		Osrednjeslovenska Settlements	Lau 2	Administrative Area	
Parma and Piacenza (IT) Living Lab		Parma and Piacenza Living Lab	Living Lab	Administrative Area	

Living lab		Indicator	Scale	Unit
		Parma and Piacenza Municipalities	Lau 2	Administrative Area
Rhein-Hunsrück (DE) Living Lab		Educational Migration	Living Lab	Administrative Area
		Rhein-Hunsrück Living Lab	Lau 2	Administrative Area
		Rhein-Hunsrück Municipalities	Living Lab	Administrative Area
Monmouthshire (UK) Living Lab		Lower Layers Super Output Areas Dec 2021	Living Lab	Administrative Area
		Lower Layers Super Output Areas Dec 2011	Living Lab	Administrative Area
		Monmouthshire LA Boundary	Living Lab	Administrative Area
		Monmouthshire Living Lab	Living Lab	Administrative Area
	Outward Migration by Age (LSOA Level, 2021 Census)	Population outflow from 1 to 15 years	Living Lab	N° of people
		Population outflow from 16 to 24 years	Living Lab	N° of people
		Population outflow from 25 to 34 years	Living Lab	N° of people
		Population outflow from 35 to 49 years	Living Lab	N° of people
		Population outflow from 50 to 64 years	Living Lab	N° of people
		Population outflow superior to 65 years	Living Lab	N° of people
		Population outflow moved out of the area, but within the associated area	Living Lab	N° of people
	Population outflow moved out of the associated area, but within England and Wales	Living Lab	N° of people	
	Trojan - Apriltsi - Ugarchin (BG) Living Lab		Trojan - Apriltsi - Ugarchin Living Lab	Living Lab
Trojan - Apriltsi - Ugarchin Capitals			Lau 2	Points
Number of beneficiaries receiving payments under the CAP			Lau 2	Number
N of SMEs receiving payment under the CAP			Lau 2	Number
N of farmers receiving payment under the CAP			Lau 2	Number
N of women farmers receiving payment under the CAP			Lau 2	Number
N of organic farmers per municipality			Lau 2	Number
N of livestock farms per municipality			Lau 2	Number
N of homesteads (not registered as farmers) per municipality			Lau 2	Number
N of apiaries per municipality			Lau 2	Number

Living lab		Indicator	Scale	Unit
		N of enterprises NACE_rev 2_A (Agriculture)	Lau 2	Number
		N of hotels and accommodations per municipality	Lau 2	Number
		N of Restaurants (all categories)	Lau 2	Number
		Beekeepers	Lau 2	Points
		Beneficiaries	Lau 2	Number
Upper Carinthia (AT) Living Lab		Self-employment rate (%)	Lau 2	Percentage (%)
		Population change 2001 to 2021 (%)	Lau 2	Percentage (%)
		Living Lab	Living Lab	Administrative Area
		Municipalities	Lau 2	Administrative Area
	Employment rate per sector	Employment rate % of primary sector - agriculture and forestry	Lau 2	Percentage (%)
		Employment rate % of secondary sector - industry and constructions	Lau 2	Percentage (%)
		Employment rate % of tertiary sector - services and public administration	Lau 2	Percentage (%)
	Commuter flows	Rate of inbound commuters (%)	Lau 2	Percentage (%)
		Rate of outbound commuters (%)	Lau 2	Percentage (%)
	Sectoral distribution of the self-employed	Proportion of self-employed in the primary sector (%)	Lau 2	Percentage (%)
		Proportion of self-employed in the secondary sector (%)	Lau 2	Percentage (%)
		Proportion of self-employed in the tertiary sector (%)	Lau 2	Percentage (%)
	Location of businesses and governmental services	Businesses and public facilities by sector category	Lau 2	Point
		Governmental services	Lau 2	Point
	Woj. świętokrzyskie (PL) Living Lab	Woj. świętokrzyskie Living Lab	Living Lab	Administrative Area
Density of Population		Density of Population LAU 2022 - 2005	Lau 2	Inhabitants/km ²
Population		Population LAU 2022 - 2005	Lau 2	Inhabitants
Share of the population at pre-working age		Share of the population at pre-working age 2022 - 2005	Lau 2	Percentage (%)
Share of the population at working age		Share of the population at working age 2022 - 2005	Lau 2	Percentage (%)
Share of the population at post-working age		Share of the population at post-working age 2022 - 2005	Lau 2	Percentage (%)

Living lab		Indicator	Scale	Unit
Woj. Mazowieckie (PL) Living Lab		Living Lab	Living Lab	Administrative Area
		LAU	Lau 2	Administrative Area
		Regions	Nuts 3	Administrative Area
		Municipalities	Lau 2	Administrative Area
		Settlements	Lau 2	Administrative Area
	Population Municipalities	Population Municipalities 2022 - 1995	Lau 2	Inhabitants
	Population Municipalities Productiveness	Preproductive Population 2021 - 2011	Lau 2	Inhabitants
		Productive Population 2021 - 2011	Lau 2	Inhabitants
		Postproductive Population 2021 - 2011	Lau 2	Inhabitants
Zajecar District (RS) Living Lab		Zajecar District Living Lab	Living Lab	Administrative Area
		Zajecar District Municipalities	Lau 2	Administrative Area
		Zajecar District Settlements	Lau 2	Administrative Area
		Zajecar District Census Division	Lau 2	Administrative Area
	Demographic Indicators	Annual change rate (%)	District Settlements	Percentage (%)
		Ageing index	District Settlements	Ratio
		Old age dependency ratio (1st variant)	District Settlements	Ratio
		Structural dependency index	District Settlements	Ratio
	Supply Chains	Alcoholic Drink Supply Chain	District Settlements	Point
		Crop Products Supply Chain	District Settlements	Point
		Eggs Supply Chain	District Settlements	Point
		Fish Supply Chain	District Settlements	Point
		Flour Supply Chains	District Settlements	Point
		Fruits, Vegetables, Mushrooms and Processed Foods Supply Chains	District Settlements	Point
		Honey Supply Chains	District Settlements	Point
		Meat and Meat Products Supply Chains	District Settlements	Point
Milk and Dairy Products Supply Chains	District Settlements	Point		
Miscellaneous Supply Chains	District Settlements	Point		

Living lab			Indicator	Scale	Unit
	Supply and Demand Locations	Mapped data (Desk based)	Farmers selling at green markets	District Settlements	Point
			Farmers selling online	District Settlements	Point
			Food Processors	District Settlements	Point
			Green Markets	District Settlements	Point
			Hotels	District Settlements	Point
			Restaurant	District Settlements	Point
			Rural Tourist Households	District Settlements	Point
		Mapped Data (Field Survey)	Buyers of products from farms	District Settlements	Point
			Buyers of small and medium enterprise products	District Settlements	Point
			Farmers	District Settlements	Point
			Hospitality Establishments	District Settlements	Point
			Small and Medium Enterprises	District Settlements	Point
			Suppliers of Hospitality Establishments	District Settlements	Point
			Suppliers of Small and Medium Enterprises	District Settlements	Point
	Structural Data on Agriculture	Utilized agricultural area (UAA) per farm (ha) (2023)	District Settlements	Hectares (ha)	
		Livestock units (LSU) per farm (2023)	District Settlements	Number	
		Annual work unit (AWU) per farm (2023)	District Settlements	Number	
		Standard output (SO) per farm (2023)	District Settlements	Euro (€)	
		Percentage of farms selling over 50% of the value of their production (%)	District Settlements	Percentage (%)	
		Percentage of farms with other gainful activities (OGA) (%)	District Settlements	Percentage (%)	
Percentage of farms selling over 50% of their production and engaged in other gainful activities (OGA)		District Settlements	Percentage (%)		
Standard output (SO) of farms selling over 50% of their production		District Settlements	Euro (€)		
Standard output (SO) of farms selling over 50% of their production and engaged in other gainful activities (OGA)		District Settlements	Euro (€)		
Farms selling over 50% of their production and engaged in meat processing		District Settlements	Number		
Farms selling over 50% of their production and engaged in meat processing	District Settlements	Number			

Living lab		Indicator	Scale	Unit
		Farms selling over 50% of their production and engaged in milk processing	District Settlements	Number
		Farms selling over 50% of their production and engaged in fruit and vegetable processing	District Settlements	Number
		Farms selling over 50% of their production and engaged in brandy making	District Settlements	Number
		Farms selling over 50% of their production and engaged in other activities connected with food processing	District Settlements	Number
		Farms selling over 50% of their production and engaged in wood processing	District Settlements	Number
		Farms selling over 50% of their production and engaged in forestry services	District Settlements	Number
		Farms selling over 50% of their production and engaged in farm tourism	District Settlements	Number
		Farms selling over 50% of their production and engaged in handicrafts	District Settlements	Number
		Farms selling over 50% of their production and engaged in energy	District Settlements	Number
		Farms selling over 50% of their production and engaged in aquaculture	District Settlements	Number
		Farms selling over 50% of their production and engaged in public utility services	District Settlements	Number
		Farms selling over 50% of their production and engaged in other activities	District Settlements	Number

3.3. Contents of the RUSTIK Viewer

Within Part B of this document, the indicators included in the RUSTIK Viewer are presented through a graphical representation that facilitates their interpretation and understanding.

The indicators are organised according to their thematic structure and subdivided into their respective subgroups, in line with the three main transitions addressed by the project (socioeconomic, environmental, and digital). For the European dataset, a complete representation of all available indicators is provided, ensuring a comprehensive and comparable overview across territories.

In contrast, for the Living Lab dataset, only a selected subset of indicators is presented. This approach reflects the heterogeneous and highly contextual nature of local data, focusing on the most representative examples to highlight the added value of the place-based methodology adopted within the project.

3.4. Quality Control Initiatives

A sustainable monitoring system must be grounded in a robust quality framework to ensure that its content remains consistent, accurate, and reliable over time. In this context, a set of targeted quality enhancement actions has been implemented to strengthen the overall performance and usability of the RUSTIK Viewer. These actions have aligned technical functionalities with user expectations, while maintaining high standards of territorial evidence relevant for rural transition policies and ensuring a professional and accessible interface.

The approach has pursued a twofold objective. First, it has improved the consistency, coherence, and precision of all contents, including the 372 indicators across the 14 Living Labs. Second, it has enhanced the performance and responsiveness of the platform, ensuring that software tools operate efficiently and effectively meet user needs.

To achieve these goals, a structured set of measures has been introduced and fully implemented. These actions support the continuous improvement of the platform and ensure its alignment with stakeholder requirements.

Consolidated Quality Activities

These actions represent setup and consolidation efforts that have already been integrated into the system to ensure long-term analytical continuity.

- **Technical Repository and Metadata Integration.** Within the RUSTIK project, a shared and open documentation system has been established through the Zenodo platform, with a specific focus on the publication of primary data generated by the Living Labs.

A selected subset of indicators included in the RUSTIK Viewer, specifically those derived from Living Lab activities (primary data), has been integrated into the Zenodo repository following a joint selection process between the project team and the individual Living Labs, ensuring both data relevance and quality.

Each dataset is accompanied by a comprehensive metadata record. To guarantee consistency across all contributions, a standardised metadata template has been

developed at project level and adapted by each Living Lab to reflect their specific context. This approach ensures harmonisation of metadata across the project while preserving the necessary flexibility to account for local particularities.

The repository therefore includes:

- **Metadata Recording.** Detailed documentation for each published dataset, including calculation methodologies, data sources, and transformation procedures, ensuring transparency, reproducibility, and long-term usability of the data beyond the project lifetime.
- **Strategic Communication and Linguistic Normalization.** The entire user interface and metadata structure have undergone a linguistic audit to ensure technical accuracy and multilingual accessibility. This prevents translation errors from hindering usability and ensures that the RUSTIK framework is interpreted correctly by regional and local stakeholders across Europe.
- **User Empowerment and Promotional Showcase (Viewer Handbook):** A comprehensive handbook has been developed as both a technical roadmap and a promotional showcase for the platform's functionalities. This document lowers the entry barrier for non-technical stakeholders and policymakers by providing:
 - **Visual Walkthroughs.** Detailed captures of core data layers, showcasing territorial trends in specific areas of interest across Europe.
 - **Thematic Relevance.** An in-depth explanation of why each transition (Socioeconomic, Environmental, and Digital) and its associated set of indicators are vital for territorial monitoring.
 - **Technical Specifications.** Clear information regarding the units of measurement, territorial scales (NUTS and LAU), and the specific geographic coverage for each dataset.
 - **Strategic Utility.** Instructions on how to extract maximum value from the data exploration tools to support evidence-based governance and what-if scenario planning.
- **Customize issue-reporting mechanism.** A user-friendly reporting system has been implemented and directly integrated into the Viewer interface, allowing stakeholders to report:
 - **Content Issues.** Obsolete data or errors in metadata descriptions.
 - **Visual Defects.** Interface bugs, map rendering issues, or zoom tool glitches.
 - **Feature Proposals.** Suggestions for new functionalities or improved visualization styles.

4. Sustainability and Maintenance Plan

4.1. Approach

Sustainability refers to the capacity of a system to remain functional over time. For the RUSTIK Viewer, this requires ensuring that the monitoring infrastructure remains operational and updated beyond the project lifecycle, with a five-year outlook.

A sustainable system is based on high-quality content and efficient software performance. Indicators must be consistent and accurate, and tools must respond effectively to user needs. Structured documentation is essential to support system maintenance, ensuring that methodologies, procedures, and technical specifications are clearly recorded and accessible.

This approach defines the conditions required to maintain technical performance and to regularly update the data infrastructure, ensuring that the RUSTIK Viewer remains operational and reliable over time. Regular updates and error-free functioning are key to ensuring long-term usability.

The plan foresees periodic updates of both Core European and Living Lab datasets, preventing technical obsolescence and ensuring correct system performance under different conditions.

The technical maintenance plan is structured around consolidated components and a recurring schedule of updates and quality checks. The following measures outline the necessary actions to be carried out in order to ensure the continued functioning of the system and are divided into Consolidated and Recurrent Functional Activities.

Consolidated Functional Activities

These actions represent the structural work already performed to ensure the long-term supportability and performance of the system.

- **Modular Architecture Deployment.** The establishment of a robust spatial data infrastructure based on PostgreSQL/PostGIS and GeoServer. This modular design ensures that individual components can be updated or replaced without compromising the entire system.
- **Documentation Management System.** all system specifications, source codes, and methodologies, organised into clear documentation pillars to prevent information loss and facilitate the work of future system administrators.

Recurrent Functional Activities

To guarantee that the Viewer continues to provide high-quality products, a strict calendar of technical follow-ups has been designed.

- **Monthly Activities** (Every Month)
 - **User Feedback & Incident Review.** On a monthly basis, user feedback and reported incidents should be reviewed to identify issues and support continuous improvement of the system. During this process, all received communications will be addressed and responded to accordingly.

- **Semi-Annual Activities** (Every 6 Months)
 - **Source Monitoring and Viewer Functionality Check.** Twice a year, the system must undergo a quality check of the indicators. This includes verifying updates in external APIs, such as Eurostat and Copernicus, to ensure that the Viewer provides up-to-date evidence for rural transition monitoring. In addition, a general check of the Viewer must be carried out, verifying that all indicators function correctly, activate properly, and display data as expected.
 - **System Patching.** Updates to the server environment, including security patches for the database and map server, to protect the platform from vulnerabilities.
 - **Documentation Audit.** Ensuring that any minor changes in data structures or software versions are recorded in the centralized documentation system to maintain an up-to-date institutional memory.

- **Annual Activities** (Every 12 Months)
 - **Indicator Refresh.** Where possible, and when updated data is readily available, new versions of existing indicator layers in the Viewer should be uploaded. While this process cannot be applied to all indicators, priority should be given to the most relevant ones. This ensures that the system reflects the latest available evidence and remains aligned with current policy needs.
 - **Nomenclature and Boundary Review.** An annual check for changes in NUTS region boundaries. If boundaries have shifted, the system administrator applies reallocation keys and recalculates historical data to ensure scientific reliability and territorial accuracy.
 - **Platform Compatibility Testing.** On an annual basis, the system should be tested against the latest versions of major web browsers (Chrome, Firefox, Edge). This ensures a consistent visual and functional experience regardless of the user's hardware or software updates.
 - **Active Bug-Hunting.** A comprehensive assessment aimed at the discovery of defects in the system. This involves testing all web tools to ensure they are in a perfect functional state and perform well in unforeseeable scenarios.

Table 8 Operational Maintenance Plan and Staff Effort Allocation.

Action Name	Frequency	Specialised Personnel to undertake the task	Dedication of Senior staff	Dedication of Junior staff
User Feedback & Incident Review	Monthly	IT Technician	1	2
Source Monitoring and Viewer Functionality Check	Semi-annual	IT Technician	5	10
System Patching	Semi-annual	IT Technician	1	2
Documentation Audit	Semi-annual	Consultant	1	3
Indicator Refresh	Annual	GIS Analyst	5	10
Nomenclature and Boundary Review	Annual	GIS Analyst	5	10
Platform Compatibility Testing	Annual	Consultant	1	1
Active Bug-Hunting	Annual	IT Technician	3	5
Total staff effort in 5 years' time			200	450

5. Final Conclusions and Next Steps

The development of the RUSTIK Data System and its integration within the RUSTIK Viewer represent a key outcome of the project, establishing a coherent and operational data infrastructure for the analysis of rural and regional transitions across Europe.

- Over the course of the project, substantial efforts have been devoted to the design, structuring, and implementation of the RUSTIK Viewer as an accessible and user-friendly platform for exploring territorial data. The system currently hosts a broad set of indicators covering the socioeconomic, environmental, and digital dimensions of rural transitions. These indicators bring together information from multiple European institutional sources alongside place-based datasets produced within the 14 Living Labs, enabling users to explore both European-wide patterns and local dynamics within a single analytical environment.
- At the current stage of the project, the Viewer can be considered fully implemented and operational. All indicators identified during the development of the database have been successfully integrated into the platform and are available through the online interface. In addition, extensive technical validation processes have been conducted to ensure the reliability and correct functioning of the system.

These verification activities have included repeated checks on data integrity, indicator visualisation, and the overall performance of the platform, confirming the robustness and stability of the Viewer.

- As the project approaches its final phase, the focus of the remaining work is shifting from system development to **consolidation and refinement**.
 - Particular attention will be dedicated to ensuring that the datasets integrated into the platform remain as up to date as possible. To this end, ongoing efforts are being made to identify more recent versions of existing datasets or newly available indicators provided by European data services and other relevant sources. When such updates become available, they will be progressively incorporated into the Viewer in order to enhance the temporal relevance and analytical value of the system.
 - In parallel, minor technical adjustments and maintenance activities will continue to be carried out in order to guarantee the long-term usability and stability of the platform. These actions include monitoring the performance of the database infrastructure, verifying compatibility with evolving software environments, and maintaining the technical components that support the Viewer.

Looking beyond the conclusion of the project, MCRIT commits to ensuring that the RUSTIK Data Viewer remains accessible and operational for a period of five years after the end of the project. During this period, in case of identified issues—either detected internally or reported by users—reasonable efforts will be made to address and resolve them as promptly as possible.

The RUSTIK Data Viewer has the potential to remain a valuable reference tool for researchers, policymakers, and territorial stakeholders interested in rural development and regional

transitions. Its modular architecture, reliance on open-source technologies, and integration of harmonised datasets provide a solid foundation for future updates, further development, or possible replication in other territorial contexts. By consolidating the work carried out during the project, the RUSTIK Viewer can continue to support evidence-based decision-making and contribute to a deeper understanding of rural transformations across Europe.

Part B

1. Introduction

Part B of this document represents the operational complement to Part A, providing a concrete and visual translation of the RUSTIK Data System in the Viewer.

Through the graphical presentation of indicators, organised by transition and thematic subgroups, this section allows for an immediate understanding of the structure, content, and analytical potential of the platform. The complete representation of European indicators, combined with a targeted selection of Living Lab indicators, enables users to grasp both the comparative European dimension and the detailed, place-based perspective.

On this basis, the RUSTIK Viewer can be considered a fully operational tool, capable of supporting the analysis of rural transitions through the effective integration of harmonised data and local information. Future activities will therefore focus on system consolidation, progressive dataset updates, and the maintenance of technical performance, ensuring long-term reliability and relevance.

Overall, the system provides a solid foundation for advanced territorial analysis and evidence-based decision-making, strengthening the role of the Viewer as a reference tool for policymakers, researchers, and territorial stakeholders.

The Rustik Information System does not directly support map generation. Map production is enabled, for the European database, by providing access links to the datasets used to build the viewer. For maps based on data developed by the Living Labs, it is necessary to request data access permission directly from the respective partners.

The images below are screenshots captured for each indicator available in the viewer; therefore, they do not include a scale and do not share a uniform cartographic base.

2. Socioeconomic Transition

This dimension analyses the fundamental structure and evolution of European society through demographic, social welfare, and economic development indicators. The objective is to provide a comprehensive view of territorial cohesion by evaluating everything from gender equality and migratory flows to physical accessibility to essential services like education, healthcare, and transport. By integrating data on labour markets and governance, this section identifies opportunity gaps and the socioeconomic resilience of various administrative regions (LAU and NUTS levels).

1.1 Demographics and Population. This section analyses the foundational landscape of a territory through the volume and dynamics of its residents. Population and density indicators at the LAU 2 scale allow for the identification of human concentration hubs as well as trends in growth or depopulation. This analysis is vital for understanding human pressure on land and forecasting future demands for resources and infrastructure based on the demographic evolution of each region.

1.1.1 Population. This group of indicators shows the total number of residents at different reference years, and the rate of population change over time at LAU 2 level, reflecting demographic size and temporal evolution.

Total Population: Reflecting demographic size.

Population Growth: Reflecting demographic temporal evolution.

1.1.2 Population density. These indicators capture how population is spatially distributed and how density has changed over time. They are essential for understanding urban pressure, land use intensity, infrastructure demand, and regional development patterns.

Population Density: Expresses the number of inhabitants per square kilometres (inhabitants/km²) at the LAU 2 scale

Population Density Growth: Captures the change in population density over the decade, expressed as the crude rate of density change per km².

1.2 Social Welfare and Inclusion. Social inclusion focuses on equity and the integration of groups. This section places special emphasis on the gender gap (analysing employment, unemployment, and indices of female achievement and disadvantage) as well as migratory flows and population diversity. These indicators help detect areas of vulnerability and evaluate whether cohesion policies are successfully creating more just, diverse, and balanced societies.

1.2.1 Gender: This group of indicators assesses gender equality in employment, unemployment, socio-economic disadvantage, and achievement. They provide insights into structural gender gaps and support the evaluation of inclusiveness and equal opportunity across regions.

Women employment proportion. Indicates the share of women employed relative to the total population at NUTS 2 scale, expressed as a percentage.

Women and men unemployment difference. Shows the gender disparity in unemployment rates, calculated as the difference between female and male unemployment percentages at NUTS 2 scale.

Female Disadvantage Index (FemDI): Quantifies women's disadvantage relative to men across socio-economic indicators, with values ranging from 1 to 100. Higher values indicate greater female disadvantage at NUTS 2 scale.

Female Achievement Index (FemAI): Measures female performance in education, health, economic participation, and political empowerment at NUTS 2 scale, ranging from 1 to 100. Higher values denote greater female achievement.

1.2.2 Migration. This group of indicators analyses the movement of people across borders and regions. They are essential for understanding demographic shifts, labour market dynamics, and the degree of social integration and diversity within different territories.

Crude rate of net migration: Captures the net population change due to migration, expressed in thousands per NUTS 3 unit.

Migration population proportion: Measures the share of total population consisting of migrants, expressed as a percentage (%) at NUTS 2 scale.

1.3 Facilities and Community Development. Access to essential services is the primary benchmark for social cohesion and quality of life. This group of indicators measures the daily support infrastructure, including education, healthcare, retail, and transport—evaluating both its physical presence and its temporal and spatial accessibility. By analysing proximity to schools, hospitals, and pharmacies, we can identify a territory’s capacity to offer equal opportunities and basic well-being to its citizens.

1.3.1 Primary Schools. These indicators evaluate the spatial distribution, availability, and accessibility of basic educational facilities. They are crucial for assessing territorial cohesion, social infrastructure coverage, and equal access to essential services for families and children.

Points of Interest - Primary Schools: Represents the number of facilities of each type located in a Local Administrative Unit (LAU 2), counting each individual point within the unit

Grid for Primary School Availability: Indicates the number of facilities accessible within a grid area of 6.25 km², measuring accessibility at the LAU 2 scale.

The RUSTIK Information System is an analytical interface providing access to meaningful data sets illuminating three key transitions in rural areas: socio-economic, environmental, and digital.

The System connects a central EU platform with regional systems at the Pilot Region level (the Living Labs interface). The Core RUSTIK European interface fosters comparability and transferability of data across regions and territories, while the Living Lab interface emphasizes locally curated datasets that answer to place-based challenges.

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Share Overlaid Accessibility to Primary School: Measures average travel time to the nearest facility, expressed in minutes at NUTS 3 scale.

Distance to Primary School: Captures the distance, in meters, from a given location to the nearest point of interest, measured at LAU 2 scale

1.3.2 Secondary Schools. This set of indicators evaluates the spatial distribution, availability, and accessibility of secondary schools. They are crucial for assessing territorial cohesion, quality of life, and equal access to basic services.

Points of Interest - Secondary Schools: Represents the number of facilities of each type located in a Local Administrative Unit (LAU 2), geolocating each individual point.

Grid for Secondary Schools Availability: Indicates the number of facilities accessible within a grid area of 6.25 km², measuring accessibility at the LAU 2 scale.

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Grid for Secondary Schools Availability

- 0 - 1
- 1 - 3
- 3 - 6
- 6 - 10
- 10 - 270

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Share Overlaid Accessibility to Secondary School: Measures average travel time to the nearest facility, expressed in minutes at NUTS 3 scale.

Distance to Secondary Schools: Captures the distance in meters from a given location to the nearest point of interest, measured at LAU 2 scale.

1.3.3. Hospitals. This set of indicators evaluates the spatial distribution, availability, and accessibility of hospitals. They are crucial for assessing territorial cohesion, quality of life, and equal access to basic services.

Points of Interest - Hospitals: Represents the number of facilities of each type located in a Local Administrative Unit (LAU 2), geolocating each individual point.

Grid for Hospital Availability: Indicates the number of facilities accessible within a grid area of 6.25 km², measuring accessibility at the LAU 2 scale.

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Grid for Hospitals Availability

- 0 - 1
- 1 - 3
- 3 - 6
- 6 - 10
- 10 - 270

Share Overlaid Accessibility to Hospitals: Measures average travel time to the nearest facility, expressed in minutes at NUTS 3 scale.

Distance to Hospitals: Captures the distance in meters from a given location to the nearest point of interest, measured at LAU 2 scale.

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Distance to Hospitals

- 0 - 6171
- 6171 - 10200
- 10200 - 14710
- 14710 - 22350
- 22350 - 243665

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1.3.4 Doctors. This set of indicators evaluates the spatial distribution and accessibility of doctors. They are crucial for assessing territorial cohesion, quality of life, and equal access to basic services.

Points of Interest - Doctors: Represents the number of facilities of each type located in a Local Administrative Unit (LAU 2), geolocating each individual point.

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Grid for Doctor Accessibility: Indicates the number of facilities accessible within a grid area of 6.25 km², measuring accessibility at the LAU 2 scale.

1.3.5 Pharmacies. This set of indicators evaluates the spatial distribution and accessibility of Pharmacies. They are crucial for assessing territorial cohesion, quality of life, and equal access to basic services.

Points of Interest - Pharmacies: Represents the number of facilities of each type located in a Local Administrative Unit (LAU 2), geolocating each individual point.

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Grid for Pharmacy Availability: Indicates the number of facilities accessible within a grid area of 6.25 km², measuring accessibility at the LAU 2 scale.

1.3.6 Train Stations. This set of indicators evaluates the spatial distribution, availability, and accessibility of Train Stations. They are crucial for assessing territorial cohesion, quality of life, and equal access to basic services.

Grid for Train Stations Availability: Indicates the number of facilities accessible within a grid area of 6.25 km², measuring accessibility at the LAU 2 scale.

Share Overlaid Accessibility to Train Stations: Measures average travel time to the nearest facility, expressed in minutes at NUTS 3 scale.

Distance to Train Stations: Captures the distance in meters from a given location to the nearest point of interest, measured at LAU 2 scale.

1.3.7 Banks. This set of indicators evaluates the spatial distribution and accessibility of Banks. They are crucial for assessing territorial cohesion, quality of life, and equal access to basic services.

Points of Interest - Banks: Represents the number of facilities of each type located in a Local Administrative Unit (LAU 2), geolocating each individual point.

Grid for Bank Accessibility: Indicates the number of facilities accessible within a grid area of 6.25 km², measuring accessibility at the LAU 2 scale.

1.3.8 Retail Shops. This set of indicators evaluates the spatial distribution and accessibility of retail shops. They are crucial for assessing territorial cohesion, quality of life, and equal access to basic services.

Points of Interest - Retail Shops: Represents the number of facilities of each type located in a Local Administrative Unit (LAU 2), geolocating each individual point.

Grid for Retail Shops Accessibility: Indicates the number of facilities accessible within a grid area of 6.25 km², measuring accessibility at the LAU 2 scale.

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 - Points of Interest - Cinemas
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1.3.9 Cinemas. This set of indicators evaluates the spatial distribution, availability, and accessibility of Cinemas. They are crucial for assessing territorial cohesion, quality of life, and equal access to basic services.

Points of Interest - Cinemas: Represents the number of facilities of each type located in a Local Administrative Unit (LAU 2), geolocating each individual point.

Grid for Cinema Availability: Indicates the number of facilities accessible within a grid area of 6.25 km², measuring accessibility at the LAU 2 scale.

Distance to Cinemas: Captures the distance in meters from a given location to the nearest point of interest, measured at LAU 2 scale.

1.4 Employment and Economic Development. This block evaluates economic vitality and labour market structures, which are essential for long-term prosperity. Through indicators ranging from sectoral specialization and unemployment rates to investment in human capital (education), this section aims to measure the financial resilience of territories. Analysis of GDP per capita and tourism capacity complements this view, offering a map of regional productivity and economic growth potential.

1.4.1 Job accessibility. This group of indicators examines labour market conditions, including unemployment and sectoral employment structure. They provide insights into economic specialization, workforce distribution, and regional labour market resilience.

Unemployment Proportion: Represents the share of the labour force that is unemployed but actively seeking employment, expressed as a percentage (%) at NUTS 2 scale.

Agriculture Sector Workers Proportion: Measures the share of the workforce employed in the agriculture sector, expressed as a percentage (%) of the total labour force at NUTS 2 scale.

Industrial Sector Workers Proportion: Measures the share of the workforce employed in the industrial sector, expressed as a percentage (%) of the total labour force at NUTS 2 scale.

Construction Sector Workers Proportion: Measures the share of the workforce employed in the construction sector, expressed as a percentage (%) of the total labour force at NUTS 2 scale.

General Service Workers Proportion: Measures the share of the workforce employed in the general service sector, expressed as a percentage (%) of the total labour force at NUTS 2 scale.

Financial Service Workers Proportion: Measures the share of the workforce employed in the financial service sector, expressed as a percentage (%) of the total labour force at NUTS 2 scale.

1.4.2 Economic Activity. These indicators assess economic performance and tourism capacity. They help evaluate economic vitality, productivity levels, and territorial competitiveness.

Tourism capacity in rooms: Represents the number of tourist rooms available per LAU 2 unit, reflecting local accommodation capacity.

GDP per capita: Expresses economic output per person, measured in euros (€) at NUTS 3 scale.

1.4.3 Education. This set of indicators measures educational attainment and early school leaving rates. They are key to understanding human capital development, employability, and long-term socio-economic prospects.

Tertiary education level (25-64) (%): Measures the percentage of individuals aged 25–64 who have completed Tertiary educational level at NUTS 3 scale.

Secondary education level (25-64) (%): Measures the percentage of individuals aged 25–64 who have completed Secondary educational level at NUTS 3 scale.

Early school leaving (18-24) (%): Measures the percentage of individuals aged 18-24 who have left formal education and training without completing upper secondary education, at NUT 3 level.

1.4.4 Sectorial Land Use. These indicators describe how land is allocated among forest, built-up, and agricultural uses. They are important for understanding economic structure, territorial specialization, and land management patterns.

Forest Proportion of Land (%): Indicates the percentage of a municipal unit's total land area covered by forests at LAU 2 scale.

Built Proportion of Land (%): Measures the share of land area covered by buildings or infrastructure at LAU 2 scale.

Agricultural Proportion of Land (%): Captures the percentage of total land area used for agricultural purposes, including crops and livestock, at LAU 2 scale

1.5 Community Engagement and Governance. Effective governance is an invisible but critical pillar for regional development. By analysing institutional quality and trust in public administrations, this section evaluates the strength of the democratic framework and transparency in public management. A high government index indicates lower corruption and greater efficiency in service delivery—factors that determine a community's ability to participate actively in its own progress and stability.

1.5.1 Trust in Administrations. This indicator assesses the quality of regional governance, including institutional effectiveness and corruption control. It provides insights into institutional trust, public sector performance, and governance capacity.

Quality of Government Index: Assesses regional governance quality, including factors such as corruption control, rule of law, and government effectiveness. Values range from 1 to 0, with higher scores indicating better governance at NUTS 2 scale.

3. Environmental Transition

The environmental transition focuses on the interaction between human activity and natural ecosystems, addressing critical challenges of climate change and sustainable land management. By monitoring climate risks—such as wildfires and extreme precipitation—and providing a detailed analysis of land use, this category assesses the health of Europe’s natural capital. These indicators measure regional adaptation capacity, the preservation of biodiversity in protected areas, and progress toward a resource-efficient, low-carbon development model.

2.1 Climate Resilience: Climate resilience is a critical safeguard for rural stability and ecological health. By monitoring wildfire risks, drought frequency, and precipitation patterns, this section assesses territorial vulnerability and adaptive capacity. High preparedness indicates a region's ability to protect natural resources and minimize socioeconomic disruptions, ensuring long-term viability in the face of global environmental change.

2.1.1 Wildfires: Measures projected changes in fire danger and historical burnt areas to assess climate-driven risks and landscape vulnerability.

Projected change in meteorological forest fire danger: Measures the projected percentage change in meteorological forest fire danger, expressed as the variation in the Standardized Severity Ratio (SSR). It provides insights into expected shifts in fire risk driven by climatic and environmental changes.

Average meteorological forest fire danger (1981-2010): Measures the average level of meteorological forest fire danger over the reference period 1981-2010, offering a historical baseline of fire risk conditions

Areas burnt by wildfires: Identifies the areas affected by wildfires, highlighting the spatial extent of land impacted by fire events.

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2.1.2 Precipitation. This group of indicators evaluates projected changes in heavy precipitation and drought frequency under different climate scenarios. They are essential for understanding future water-related risks, climate vulnerability, and adaptation needs.

Projected changes in heavy precipitation in winter: Measures the projected percentage change in the frequency or intensity of heavy precipitation events during the winter months, reflecting potential climate change impacts on seasonal rainfall patterns.

Projected changes in heavy precipitation in summer: Measures the projected percentage change in heavy precipitation events during the summer months, indicating expected alterations in rainfall intensity and frequency.

Drought Frequency change 2041 -2071 RCP 4.5: Measures the projected variation in the frequency of drought events between 2041 and 2071 under the moderate greenhouse gas emissions scenario RCP 4.5, indicating potential climate-driven changes in drought occurrence.

Drought Frequency change 2041 -2070 RCP 8.5: Measures the projected variation in the frequency of drought events between 2041 and 2070 under the high-emission scenario RCP 8.5, reflecting potential increases in drought risk under more severe climate change conditions.

2.2. Climate Resilience. represent the foundational capital and cultural identity of rural landscapes. By monitoring protected areas, forest density, and biodiversity-rich zones, this section evaluates the health of vital ecosystems and the preservation of a territory's natural legacy. Strategic conservation ensures the sustainable management of environmental assets, safeguarding the ecological integrity and historical values that define rural regions for future generations.

2.2.1 Forestal Areas. These indicators describe forest distribution, structure, density, and changes over time. They support the assessment of ecosystem health, biodiversity, carbon storage capacity, and land management practices.

Forest Type (2018): Classifies Forest areas into thematic categories, distinguishing between non-forest areas, broadleaved forests, and coniferous forests.

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Tree Cover Density (2018): Measures the proportion of land covered by tree canopy in 2018, expressed as a percentage ranging from 0% to 100%.

Tree Cover Change Mask (2015–2018): Identifies changes in tree cover over the period 2015–2018, categorizing areas as unchanged without tree cover, new tree cover, loss of tree cover, or unchanged with tree cover.

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Living lab finder

Disclaimer

Tree Cover Change Mask (2015 - 2018)

- 0: unchanged areas with no tree cover
- 1: new tree cover
- 2: loss of tree cover
- 10: unchanged areas with tree cover
- 254: unclassifiable in any of parent status layers
- 255: outside area

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Dominant Leaf Type (2018): Indicates the prevailing forest leaf type in 2018, classified as either broadleaved or coniferous.

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 - Dominant Leaf Type (2018) ⓘ ⌵
 - ▣ Protected Areas and Biodiversity
- ▾ Living lab finder
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2.2.2 Protected Areas and Biodiversity. This group identifies protected and ecologically significant areas. It is fundamental for evaluating conservation coverage, environmental protection efforts, and ecosystem preservation.

Natura 2000 Protected Areas: Identifies areas designated under the European Union’s Natura 2000 network for the conservation of habitats and species of community interest.

RUSTIK INFORMATION SYSTEM

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Natura 2000 Protected Areas

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Emerald Protected Areas: Identifies areas designated under the Emerald Network

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Mountain Areas grid: Identifies territories characterized by significant altitude or steep slopes,

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Mountain Areas

Funded by the European Union

2.3 Land Cover and Land Use. provides a comprehensive record of the physical landscape and its ongoing transformations. By monitoring built-up areas, agricultural footprints, and natural grasslands, this section evaluates the dynamic balance between human development and environmental preservation. Tracking these spatial shifts is essential for managing urban sprawl and protecting productive land, ensuring that territorial growth remains sustainable and synchronized with the region's natural boundaries.

2.3.1 Land Use. These indicators provide detailed information on land cover distribution and changes across urban, rural, coastal, and riparian areas. They are crucial for spatial planning, environmental monitoring, and sustainable land management.

Urban Atlas Land Cover/Land Use (2018): Provides detailed land cover and land use information for urban and surrounding rural areas, with a minimum mapping unit of 0.25 hectares for urban classes and 1 hectare for selected rural classes.

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 - Coastal Zones Land Cover/Land Use (i) [list icon]

- Living lab finder
- Disclaimer

Urban Atlas Land Cover / Land Use (2018)

code_2018

- 11100: Continuous Urban fabric (S.L. > 80%)
- 11210: Discontinuous Dense Urban Fabric (S.L.: 50% - 80%)
- 11220: Discontinuous Medium Density Urban Fabric (S.L.: 30% - 50%)
- 11230: Discontinuous Low Density Urban Fabric (S.L.: 10% - 30%)
- 11240: Discontinuous very low density urban fabric (S.L. < 10%)
- 11300: Isolated Structures
- 12100: Industrial, commercial, public, military and private units
- 12210: Fast transit roads and associated land
- 12220: Other roads and associated land
- 12230: Railways and associated land
- 12300: Port areas
- 12400: Airports
- 13100: Mineral extraction and dump sites
- 13300: Construction sites

CLC+ Backbone 2018: Classifies the dominant land cover type based on 11 basic land cover classes, offering a harmonized overview of land cover patterns.

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CLC + Backbone (2018) ✕

- Sealed
- Woody needle leaved trees
- Woody Broadleaved deciduous trees
- Woody Broadleaved evergreen trees
- Low-growing woody plants
- Permanent herbaceous
- Periodically herbaceous
- Lichens and mosses
- Non and sparsely vegetated
- Water
- Snow and ice
- Outside area
- No data

Coastal Zones Land Cover/Land Use: Classifies land cover and land use within coastal zones into 71 thematic classes, supporting detailed coastal spatial analysis

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 - ▼ Land Cover
 - Urban Atlas Land Cover / Land Use (2018) ⓘ
 - CLC + Backbone (2018) ⓘ
 - Coastal Zones Land Cover/Land Use ⓘ
- ▶ Living lab finder
- ▶ Disclaimer

Coastal Zones Land Cover/Land Use Change (2012–2018): Identifies changes in land cover and land use within coastal zones between 2012 and 2018, based on 71 thematic classes.

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 - Coastal Zones Land Cover/Land Use ⓘ
 - Coastal Zones Land Cover/Land Use Change (2012-2018) ⓘ
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Coastal Zones Land Cover/Land Use Change (2012-2018)

- 11110 Continuous urban fabric (IMD ≥80%)
- 11120 Dense urban fabric (IMD ≥30-80%)
- 11130 Low density fabric (IMD <30%)
- 11210 Industrial, commercial, public and military units (other)
- 11220 Nuclear energy plants and associated land
- 12100 Road networks and associated land
- 12200 Railways and associated land
- 12310 Cargo port
- 12320 Passenger port
- 12330 Fishing port
- 12340 Naval port
- 12350 Marinas
- 12360 Local multi-functional harbours
- 12370 Shipyards
- 12400 Airports and associated land

2.3.2 Built up Areas. Evaluates urbanization levels, building heights, and impervious surfaces to monitor urban expansion and structural density.

Impervious Built-up 2018: Identifies areas covered by impervious built-up surfaces in 2018, distinguishing between built and non-built areas.

Urban Atlas Building Height 2012: Measures the vertical dimension of buildings in core urban areas, expressed in meters, providing insights into urban density and structural development patterns.

Degree of Urbanization: Classifies areas according to population density and settlement size, distinguishing between urban, semi-urban, and rural areas.

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 - ▶ Land Cover
 - ▼ Built-up area
 - Impervious Built-up (2018) ⓘ
 - Urban Atlas Building Height (2012) ⓘ
 - Degree of Urbanization ⓘ
- ▶ Living lab finder
- ▶ Disclaimer

Degree of Urbanization

- Urban areas
- Peri-urban areas
- Rural areas

2.3.3 Imperviousness. These indicators measure the degree and evolution of land sealing. They are important for assessing urban expansion, environmental pressure, surface runoff, and ecosystem fragmentation.

Imperviousness Density 2018: Measures the proportion of land covered by impervious surfaces such as asphalt and concrete in 2018, expressed as a percentage from 0% (no sealing) to 100% (fully sealed).

Imperviousness Change 2015–2018: Measures the percentage change in impervious surfaces between 2015 and 2018, ranging from -100% (total decrease) to +100% (total increase), indicating trends in land sealing.

Imperviousness Classified Change (2015–2018): Categorizes changes in impervious surfaces between 2015 and 2018 into six classes: unchanged no sealing, new cover, loss of cover, unchanged sealed, increased sealing, and decreased sealing.

2.3.4 Grassland. These indicators identify grassland areas and their changes over time. They contribute to understanding ecosystem services, biodiversity conservation, and agricultural transitions.

Grassland 2018: Identifies areas covered by grassland ecosystems in 2018.

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 - Land Cover
 - Built-up area
 - Imperviousness
 - ▾ Grassland
 - Grassland (2018) (i) [list icon]
 - Grassland Change (2015 - 2018) (i) [list icon]
- ▾ Living lab finder
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Grassland Change 2015–2018: Indicates whether grassland areas experienced change between 2015 and 2018.

2.3.5 Agriculture. This indicator highlights land dedicated to agricultural use. It is relevant for assessing food production capacity, rural land management, and landscape structure.

Agricultural Area (2018): Identifies land designated for agricultural use in 2018, including both cultivated and uncultivated areas used for farming activities.

2.4 Environment. provides assessment of the ecological health and liveability of territories. By tracking air quality metrics and vegetation vitality indices, this section evaluates the direct impact of atmospheric conditions and biomass health on regional well-being. Ensuring a clean and healthy environment is vital for both public health and economic attractiveness, safeguarding the essential natural conditions that allow rural communities to flourish and sustain their unique quality of life.

2.4.1 Water: These indicators describe the presence of water bodies, wet surfaces, and riparian land cover dynamics. They are essential for water resource management, ecological protection, and climate adaptation.

Water and Wetness Status 2018: Identifies the presence of water bodies and wet surfaces in 2018.

Riparian Zones Land Cover/Land Use: Classifies land cover and land use within riparian zones using multiple thematic classes.

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Riparian Zones (2018)

- 1.1.1.1 Continuous urban fabric (I.M.D. ≥ 80%)
- 1.1.1.2 Dense urban fabric (I.M.D. ≥ 30-80%)
- 1.1.1.3 Low density fabric (I.M.D. < 30%)
- 1.1.2.0 Industrial, commercial and military units
- 1.2.1.0 Road networks and associated land
- 1.2.2.0 Railways and associated land
- 1.2.3.0 Port areas and associated land
- 1.2.4.0 Airports and associated land
- 1.3.1.0 Mineral extraction, dump and construction sites
- 1.3.2.0 Land without current use
- 1.4.0.0 Green urban, sport and leisure facilities
- 2.1.1.0 Arable irrigated and non-irrigated land
- 2.1.2.0 Greenhouses
- 2.2.0.0 Permanent crops
- 2.2.1.0 Vineyards, fruit trees and berry plantations

Riparian Zones Land Cover/Land Use Change (2012–2018): Identifies changes in land cover and land use within riparian zones between 2012 and 2018, based on 55 thematic classes

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 - Riparian Zones (2018) ⓘ
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 - Air Quality
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Riparian Zones changes (2012 - 2018)

- 1.1.1.1 Continuous urban fabric (I.M.D. ≥ 80%)
- 1.1.1.2 Dense urban fabric (I.M.D. ≥ 30-80%)
- 1.1.1.3 Low density fabric (I.M.D. < 30%)
- 1.1.2.0 Industrial, commercial and military units
- 1.2.1.0 Road networks and associated land
- 1.2.2.0 Railways and associated land
- 1.2.3.0 Port areas and associated land
- 1.2.4.0 Airports and associated land
- 1.3.1.0 Mineral extraction, dump and construction sites
- 1.3.2.0 Land without current use
- 1.4.0.0 Green urban, sport and leisure facilities
- 2.1.1.0 Arable irrigated and non-irrigated land
- 2.1.2.0 Greenhouses
- 2.2.0.0 Permanent crops
- 2.2.1.0 Vineyards, fruit trees and berry plantations

Funded by the European Union

2.4.2 Air quality. This group of indicators measures concentrations of major air pollutants. They are critical for assessing environmental health, public health risks, and compliance with air quality standards.

Air Quality – Ozone ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$): Measures the concentration of ozone in the air, expressed in micrograms per cubic meter per day.

Air Quality – PM10 ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$): Measures the concentration of particulate matter (PM10) in the air, expressed in micrograms per cubic meter per day.

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 - Air quality of PM10 [$\mu\text{g}^*/\text{d}/\text{m}^3$] ⓘ
 - Air quality of PM2.5 [$\mu\text{g}^*/\text{d}/\text{m}^3$] ⓘ
- Living lab finder
- Disclaimer

Air quality of PM10 [$\mu\text{g}^*/\text{d}/\text{m}^3$]

Value

High : 50 - Low : 0

Funded by the European Union

Air Quality. PM2.5 ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$): Measures the concentration of fine particulate matter (PM2.5) in the air, expressed in micrograms per cubic meter per day.

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 - Air quality of PM10 [$\mu\text{g}^* \text{d}/\text{m}^3$]
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Air quality of PM2.5 [$\mu\text{g}^* \text{d}/\text{m}^3$]

Value

High : 50 - Low : 0

Funded by the European Union

2.5 Sustainable Development. represents the strategic transition toward a low-carbon economy and long-term energy autonomy. By tracking renewable energy production potentials, such as solar, wind, and hydropower, this section assesses a region’s capacity to harness clean, local resources. Promoting sustainable energy systems reduces environmental impact and fosters territorial resilience, ensuring that rural growth contributes to global climate goals while strengthening the regional economy for the future.

2.5.1 Energy. These indicators quantify renewable energy production from solar, wind (onshore), and hydropower sources. They provide insights into the energy transition, regional renewable capacity, and progress toward sustainability goals.

Solar Production: Measures the total amount of energy generated from solar sources, expressed in megawatt-hours (MWh).

Onshore Production: Measures the total amount of energy generated from onshore sources, expressed in megawatt-hours (MWh).

Hydropower Production: Measures the total amount of energy generated from hydropower sources, expressed in megawatt-hours (MWh).

4. Digital Transition

This transition examines the level of technological maturity and the connectivity infrastructure that supports the modernization of European regions. It primarily focuses on the quality and availability of digital services, measuring citizens' actual access to high-speed fixed and mobile networks. This dimension is essential for understanding the narrowing of the digital divide and the ability of territories to integrate into a globalized economy that increasingly relies on seamless data transfer and online service delivery.

3.1 Quality of Digital Service: This group of indicators evaluates the performance and availability of telecommunications infrastructure. It measures the accessibility of high-speed networks, reflecting a region's readiness for digital integration, remote work, and modern economic activities.

Access to high-speed mobile network: Measures wireless connectivity performance and coverage (Mbps), reflecting the quality of mobile data infrastructure for users on the move.

Access to high-speed fixed network: Evaluates the capacity and speed (Mbps) of broadband connections, essential for high-volume data exchange and digital business operations.

5. Living Labs

From participatory mapping of quality of life to the digital tracking of local supply chains, the following provides an overview of the 14 Living Labs that serve as the technical and social laboratories of the RUSTIK project and some of their indicators.

This Living Lab focuses on land management through indicators such as the ratio between landowners and inhabitants and the average size of land plots.

The Viewer allows for the visualization of the prioritization of settlements for the "model settlement" instrument, integrating cadastral and biophysical data to help local authorities manage land fragmentation and prevent wildfire risks through agricultural recovery.

Prioritisation of settlements for "Model Settlement" instrument

Average number of land plots per landowner

Ratio between landowner and inhabitants at municipal level

Garfagnana - Lunigiana (IT) Living Lab

RUSTIK INFORMATION SYSTEM

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Rural areas overview

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- Facilities and Community Service Accessibility
- Galore (EU)
- Garfagnana - Lunigiana (IT)
- Garfagnana and Lunigiana Living Lab
- Garfagnana and Lunigiana Common

Living Lab folder

Disclaimer

The Living Lab (LL) identified two main transition challenges: valorising the multifunctional role of forestry as part of the broader climate-environmental transition and at the same time the community regeneration in the context of the demographic decline of mountain areas since they are strongly interlinked.

The LL integrates the two challenges by developing an approach based on partnerships of different actors working on forest valorisation.

**Indicator available for all Living Lab.*

Points of Interest for Commercial Activities*

Points of Interest for Restauration*

Points of Interest for General Services*

Gloucestershire (UK) Living Lab

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Rural areas overview

Context

Geographical area: Geragiana - Lungsani (IT) Gloucestershire (UK)

Living Lab filter

Gloucestershire Living Lab

Gloucestershire forests

Average download speed (Mbps)

Average upload speed (Mbps)

Number of connections less than 2Mbps (number of area)

Full fibre take up (% of full fibre coverage)

The LL is concerned with the digital transition challenge in two ways:

- by working with rural voluntary and community sector health and social service providers to improve data collection and analysis effectiveness, to achieve a more detailed understanding of client needs and service impacts, as well as deeper appreciation of how local data could inform higher level (e.g. county) policies;
- to secure a commitment in the county's new digital strategy to include more rural and community-level data.

Average Download Speed

Average Upload Speed

Number of connections less than 2Mbps

Full fibre-take up

Woj. Mazowieckie (PL) Living Lab

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- Palma and Placencia (GT)
- Rhein-Hunsrück (DE)
- Meissourthale (UK)
- Trapani - Agrigò - Ugenten (BG)
- Neckargenau-Oberamt (AT)
- Woj. Świętokrzyskie (PL)
- Woj. Mazowieckie (PL)
- Living Lab

Living Lab Finder

Disclaimer

The initiative investigates the development challenges of the Szydłowiec district, a predominantly rural area facing economic transition.

By combining surveys, business data analysis, and experimental activities, it explores how local resources, particularly chocolate flint, can stimulate entrepreneurship and support a more diversified economy. Early findings indicate that residents and stakeholders see strong potential in leveraging these assets to enhance economic activity, reinforce local networks, and build a distinctive regional identity.

Settlements

Regions

Municipalities

Monmouthshire (UK) Living Lab

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 - Lower Ladder Super Output Areas (Dec 2021)
- Outward Migration by Age (LSOA Level, 2021 Census)
 - Population outflow from 1 to 15 years
 - Population outflow from 16 to 24 years
 - Population outflow from 25 to 34 years

Living Lab Hub
Dashboard

Population ageing has implications for its present and future economy, the social sustainability of the region's communities, and the public health and social care offering in the region as the demand pressures of an ageing population combined with the reduced revenue resulting from a decrease in the working-age population. The goal is to understand the drivers of demographic change and ways to achieve better demographic balance through retaining/attracting younger people to live and work in the county.

Population outflow from 16 to 24 years

Population outflow within England and Wales

Population outflow moved out of the area, but within the associated areas

North Karelia (FI) Living Lab

The data experiment seeks to help companies and policymakers to enable North Karelia to retain its foreign migrants, thus reducing population decline. Accordingly, its Theory of Change is based on a two-pronged approach.

On the one hand, it assumes that by helping companies develop their skills to integrate foreigners into the workplace, and on the other hand, it is assumed that with better and more accurate information, municipalities can alter their policies to retain foreigners more effectively.

Percent of population over 65 years

Population (LAU2)

Percent of population with foreign mothertongue

Osona - Sant Miquel de Balenyà (ES) Living Lab

The challenge of the Living Lab is to enhance the quality of life (QoL) in Sant Miquel de Balenyà, with a specific focus on social cohesion and equity, climate resilience, and balanced social and economic competitiveness. The means to achieve this goal will be to improve current territorial and urban planning.

Neighborhood walking spaces

Neighborhood climate shelters

Neighborhood dangerous spaces

Osrednjeslovenska (SI) Living Lab

RUSTIK
INFORMATION SYSTEM

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- Osrednjeslovenska (SI)
- Osrednjeslovenska Living Lab
- Osrednjeslovenska Municipalities
- Osrednjeslovenska Settlements
- Parma and Piacenza (IT)
- Rhein-Hunsrück (DE)
- Monmouthshire (UK)
- Troyen - Apittai - Ugarchin (BG)

The experiment addresses food loss and waste (FLW) by redistributing surplus food to marginalized groups. This approach tackles environmental impacts while simultaneously fostering social inclusion and well-being.

*Indicator available for all Living Lab.

Point of Interest for Sports and Leisure*

Points of Interest for
Touristic Information*

Parma and Piacenza (IT) Living Lab

RUSTIK INFORMATION SYSTEM

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The System connects a central EU platform with regional systems at the Pilot Region level (the Living Lab interface). The Core RUSTIK European interface fosters comparability and transferability of data across regions and territories, while the Living Lab interface emphasizes locally curated datasets that answer to place-based challenges.

Rural areas overview

- North Karelia (FI)
- Dopna - Sant Miquel de Balentó (ES)
- Černošice (CZ)
- Parma and Piacenza (IT)**
- Parma and Piacenza Living Lab
- Parma and Piacenza Municipalities
- Rhein-Hunsrück (DE)
- Honoufthale (UK)
- Troyan - April - Jigarden (BG)

Living Lab Finder
Disclaimer

The Living Lab focused on strengthening water management governance in the Po Region, particularly in times of crisis, by addressing the lack of an adequate monitoring system. Effective planning of water distribution requires reliable data on weather conditions, crop water needs, and local productivity potential.

*Indicator available for all Living Lab.

Points of interest for General Services*

Points of Interest for Restauration*

Points of interest for Commercial Activities*

Rhein-Hunsrück (DE) Living Lab

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Rural areas overview

- Concord
- North Karelia (FI)
- Osona - Sant Miquel de Balenyà (ES)
- Ovseščevskaja (SI)
- Parma and Piacenza (IT)
- Rhein-Hunsrück (DE)**
 - Rhein-Hunsrück Living Lab**
 - Rhein-Hunsrück municipalities
 - Educational Migration
- Hörsinghausen (UK)

Living Lab Profile

Disclaimer

The Rhein-Hunsrück district, despite being economically stronger than many rural German regions, continues to face challenges linked to a shortage of skilled labour and unfilled apprenticeship positions. These issues are becoming more acute with the retirement of the baby boomer generation and the decline of the 18–24 age group.

The Living Lab set out to investigate this “mismatch problem” between young people and regional employers through a data experiment combining surveys, expert interviews, focus groups and secondary data. The aim was to better understand young people’s aspirations, the difficulties employers encounter in filling vacancies, and how to improve communication and information flows between the two groups.

**Indicator available for all Living Lab.*

Points of Interest for Restauration*

Educational Migration

Points of interest for Culture*

Woj. świętokrzyskie (PL) Living Lab

The Świętokrzyskie region is very attractive for tourists and is located close to several large agglomerations. However, rural areas in this region are characterized by a large migration outflow and a lack of jobs.

The aim of LL Świętokrzyskie is to diagnose the state of and prepare assumptions regarding the development of rural tourism for the future Tourism Development Strategy of the Świętokrzyskie Voivodeship. It is assumed that the primary goal will be achieved, which is to stop unfavourable demographic processes in rural areas of the Świętokrzyskie region and diversify their economic development through promotion and creation of new tourist products.

Density of Population LAU 2022

Share of Population at pre-working age 2022

Share of Population at working age 2022

Troyan - Apriltsi - Ugarchin (BG) Living Lab

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Rural areas overview

Content

- Mainmouthshire (UK)
- Troyan - Apriltsi - Ugarchin (BG)
 - Troyan - Apriltsi - Ugarchin Living Lab
 - Troyan - Apriltsi - Ugarchin Capital
 - Number of beneficiaries receiving payments under the CAP
 - N of beneficiaries receiving payments under the CAP
 - N of farmers receiving payments under the CAP
 - N of animal farmers receiving CAP payments

Living Lab Finder

December

The challenge identified was the underexplored potential of the rural food system as a resource for local development. The Rustik experiment aimed to provide an in-depth analysis of the rural food system in the region and to suggest data-driven solutions to develop local food policy.

Upper Carinthia (AT) Living Lab

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Rural areas overview

- Connect
- Hronouhřahle (SK)
- Trnava - Apurba - Ugarin (BG)
- Nockregion-Oberkärnten (AT)
- Living Lab
 - Gemeinden / Municipalities
 - Anteil der Selbstständigen an den Erwerbstätigen (%) / Self-employment rate (%)
 - Bevölkerungsentwicklung 2001 bis 2021 (%) / Population change 2001 to 2021 (%)
 - Beschäftigungssituation nach Sektoren / Employment rate per sector
- Living Lab finder
- Disclaimer

In the Nockregion-Oberkärnten, demographic challenges such as population decline, ageing, and youth and female out-migration threaten regional vitality. The Living Lab focused on strengthening socio-economic resilience by supporting Small Rural Businesses (SRBs), which play a crucial but often underrepresented role in regional development. SRBs provide essential services, create diverse job opportunities, and act as anchors for community stability, but face major constraints including labour shortages, administrative burdens, limited training opportunities, and poor transport connections.

Self-employment rate

Rate of outbound commuters

Governmental services

Zaječar District (RS) Living Lab

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Rural areas overview

- **Context**
 - Hochregion-Oberkarnten (AT)
 - Wipj. Subpobryskje (PL)
 - Wipj. Pannowickie (PL)
 - Zaječar District (RS)
 - Zaječar District Living Lab
 - Zaječar District Municipalities
 - Zaječar District Settlements
 - Zaječar District Census Division
 - Demographic Indicators
- Living Lab Finder**
- Disclaimer**

The Living Lab in Zaječar focuses on improving economic outcomes by fostering short food supply chains that link local farmers with the growing tourism sector. Currently, tourism centres depend heavily on food from outside the region, as local producers play only a minor role.

By gathering data from farmers, food producers, and tourism operators, the Lab aims to support evidence-based policies and better supply chain coordination, while also mapping stakeholders, supply flows, and barriers to integration.

Mapped data (Desk Based)

Supply Chains

Mapped data (Field Survey)